

ELECTRE I approach for multi-criteria group decision-making in single-valued neutrosophic N-soft environment

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Abstract: The single-valued neutrosophic N-soft set model is a superior tool for capturing ambiguity and incompleteness in real-life circumstances. In this paper, we extend the ELECTRE I method to the single-valued neutrosophic N-soft ELECTRE I method in multi-criteria group decision-making environment. To explain the outranking relationship among alternatives with respect to different parameters, this new technique is developed by introducing the ideas of strong, midrange, and weak single-valued neutrosophic N-soft concordance and discordance sets. Also, we propose an algorithm for the proposed method along with a flowchart. Finally, an illustrative example is solved to validate and prove the relevance of our proposed method

Keywords: Neutrosophic set, single-valued neutrosophic N-soft set, ELECTRE I method, outranking relation, concordance and discordance sets.

1. Introduction

Multi-criteria group decision-making (MCGDM), which enables teams of experts to assess and rank several possibilities according to a set of criteria, has become an essential methodology in several sectors. This approach delivers a structured framework for managing difficult decision-making situations, improving teamwork, and assisting professionals in various fields, including the social sciences, economics, environmental studies, and healthcare, in coming to logical, informed judgements. [1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7]. The use of MCGDM procedures has become increasingly popular in real-world settings that call for organised decision-making, like resource management, urban development, and sustainability planning [8, 9].

Numerous MCGDM models, including TOPSIS [10], PROMETHEE [11], VIKOR [12], ELECTRE [13], MABAC [14], and KEMIRA [15], have been created to successfully solve these challenges. Across a variety of fields, these techniques have been used to assist decision-makers in organising complicated data and prioritising options when competing standards are involved. For example, TOPSIS and VIKOR are frequently utilised in project management and supplier selection because of their ability to reliably evaluate options according to how close they are to perfect solutions [16, 17]. Out of the various decision-making techniques, the ELECTRE (ELimination and Choice Expressing REality) approach is one of the most successful methods which makes the pairwise comparison of alternatives by outranking relation and offering as accurate and suitable a set of actions as feasible by removing alternatives that are outranked by others, depending on several criteria. Furthermore, new developments have shown how well blended decision-making paradigms work in domains like precision livestock management, underscoring the adaptability of MCGDM approaches in challenging decision-making situations [18, 19].

Further, Roy [20] drew attention to the fluctuation of distinct objects in the reference set by inventing ELECTRE-I, an enhanced version of ELECTRE. Again, Several researchers generalized and developed other innovative methods such as ELECTRE II, ELECTRE III, ELECTRE IV, ELECTRE TRI-C, and ELECTRE IS [21, 22, 23, 24]. These models are being used more and more to solve complicated decision-making problems in domains where managing multi-dimensional criteria is crucial, such as transportation, finance, medical science, and agriculture [25, 26]. In order to increase ELECTRE's efficacy in predictive and real-time decision contexts, recent research has presented hybrid models that include ELECTRE with machine learning and optimisation techniques [27, 28].

Fuzzy set (FS) theory, first presented by Zadeh [29], has been frequently used in conjunction with MCGDM techniques to address ambiguity and uncertainty in decision-making. To deal with hesitation and imprecision in data, fuzzy extensions such as intuitionistic fuzzy sets (IFSs), Pythagorean fuzzy sets (PyFSs), and q-rung orthopair fuzzy sets (qROFSs) have been employed [30, 31, 32, 33]. These modifications have been used in fields like risk assessment and medical diagnostics that demand high accuracy levels. Building on these ideas, Smarandache [34, 35] created neutrosophic sets (NSs), which manage data fusion and complicated ambiguities frequently found in large-scale decision-making by introducing separate truth, indeterminacy, and falsity membership functions. Neutrosophic extensions, like the single-valued neutrosophic set (SVNS) [36], have been successfully used in fields where processing nuanced information is essential, such as information technology and engineering [37, 38, 39, 40, 41].

Soft set theory, introduced by Molodtsov [42] gives MCGDM an additional degree of adaptability. Which provides binary evaluations of objects, which might be restrictive when used in real-world scenarios where non-binary evaluations are necessary. When assessments must contain more nuanced, graded evaluations, traditional mathematical models like FSs, IFSs, and NSs also fail. Non-binary ratings, which might be represented by stars, dots, grades, or other generalised multilevel values, are frequently required for ranking and evaluation in the real world. The N-soft set [43], an improved model of soft sets that better captures graded evaluations, was introduced to close this gap. Recent uses of soft and N-soft sets show their value in real-time decision-making situations and dynamic systems, like automated monitoring and disaster management [44, 45].

In this paper, we propose a novel adaptation of these methods by developing the SVN_NSS ELECTRE I approach, a model that combines the flexibility of single-valued neutrosophic N-soft sets (SVN_NSS) with the robust outranking structure of ELECTRE I. By offering a more generalised model that can handle uncertain, partial, and graded data, our method aims to overcome the shortcomings of current MCGDM approaches. For group decision-making in settings where ambiguity and the requirement for multi-level evaluations are common, the SVN_NSS ELECTRE I technique is especially well-suited.

The following is the structure of the research paper: In Section 2, certain fundamental definitions regarding neutrosophic N-soft sets are recalled. The notion of SVN_NSS is proposed and some of its algebraic operations are defined. In Section 3, a mathematical explanation of the MCGDM problem, as well as some important terminologies related to the SVN_NSS -ELECTRE I techniques, are described. Section 4 provides a flowchart and the algorithm for the proposed SVN_NSS -ELECTRE I approach. In Section 5, a numerical example of a site selection problem is solved as an application of the proposed algorithm. Finally, Section 6 concludes the work with recommendations for future work.

2. Preliminaries

In this section, we will go through some basic concepts and some of the impacts of N-soft and neutrosophic sets, which will be useful in the coming sections.

Definition 2.1. [29] Let Σ be the universal set of discourse. A fuzzy set Ψ on Σ is an object of the form $\Psi = \{(\zeta, \mu_\Psi(\zeta)) | \zeta \in \Sigma\}$, where $\mu_\Psi : \Sigma \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is the membership function of Ψ , the value $\mu_\Psi(\zeta)$ is the grade of membership of ζ in Ψ .

Definition 2.2. [34] Let Σ be a space of objects or points, and let $\zeta \in \Sigma$ be a generic element. A neutrosophic set N over Σ is defined by a truth membership function T_N , an indeterminacy membership function I_N , and a falsity-membership function F_N , where for each $\zeta \in \Sigma$, $T_N(\zeta)$, $I_N(\zeta)$, and $F_N(\zeta)$, are real standard or non-standard subsets of $]0^-, 1^+[$. That is $T_N, I_N, F_N : \Sigma \rightarrow]0^-, 1^+[$.

Definition 2.3. [6] Let Σ be a space of objects or points, and let $\zeta \in \Sigma$ be a generic element. A single-valued neutrosophic set S over Σ is defined by a truth membership function T_S , an indeterminacy membership function I_S , and a falsity-membership function F_S , where for each $\zeta \in \Sigma$, $T_S(\zeta)$, $I_S(\zeta)$, $F_S(\zeta) \in [0, 1]$. It can be represented as:

- If Σ is continuous, then

$$S = \int_{\Sigma} \langle T_S(\zeta), I_S(\zeta), F_S(\zeta) \rangle / \zeta, \quad \zeta \in \Sigma$$

- If $\Sigma = \{\zeta_1, \zeta_2, \dots, \zeta_n\}$ is discrete, then

$$S = \sum_1^n \langle T_S(\zeta), I_S(\zeta), F_S(\zeta) \rangle / \zeta, \quad \zeta \in \Sigma$$

Definition 2.4. [42] Let Σ be the universal set with parameter set K . A soft set over Σ is a pair $\langle \aleph, L \rangle$, where \aleph is a function from L to $P(\Sigma)$, where $P(\Sigma)$ is the power set of Σ and $L \subseteq K$.

Definition 2.5. [46] A neutrosophic soft set over a universal set Σ with parameter set K is a pair $\langle \aleph, L \rangle$, where \aleph is a mapping from L to $NS(\Sigma)$, where $NS(\Sigma)$ is the set of all neutrosophic sets over Σ and $L \subseteq K$.

For each $\varpi \in L$, $\aleph(\varpi)$ is a neutrosophic set such that $\aleph(\varpi) = \{(\zeta, T_{\aleph(\varpi)}(\zeta), I_{\aleph(\varpi)}(\zeta), F_{\aleph(\varpi)}(\zeta)) \mid \zeta \in \Sigma\}$, where $T_{\aleph(\varpi)}(\zeta), I_{\aleph(\varpi)}(\zeta), F_{\aleph(\varpi)}(\zeta) \in [0, 1]$ are the truth membership degree, indeterminacy membership degree, and falsity membership degree respectively.

Definition 2.6. [43] Let Σ be the set of objects and let K be the set of parameters with $L \subseteq K$. Let $O_G = \{0, 1, 2, \dots, N - 1\}$ be the collection of ordered grades where $N \in \{2, 3, \dots\}$. Then the triplet (\aleph, L, N) is called an N-soft set over Σ , where for all $\zeta \in \Sigma, \varpi \in L$, and, $g_{L(\varpi)} \in O_G$, $\aleph : L \rightarrow 2^{\Sigma \times O_G}$ is a map defined by $\aleph(\varpi) = (\zeta, g_{L(\varpi)})$.

Definition 2.7. [47] Let Σ be the universal set with set of attributes K and $L \subseteq \Sigma$. Let $O_G = \{0, 1, 2, \dots, N - 1\}$ be the collection of ordered grades where $N \in \{2, 3, \dots\}$. Then a neutrosophic N-soft set over Σ , denoted by Γ_L , is a triplet (\aleph, θ, N) , where $\theta = (\Gamma, L, N)$ is a neutrosophic soft set over Σ . That is,

$$\Gamma_L = \{(\varpi, \Pi_L(\varpi)) : \Pi_L(\varpi) = \{(\zeta, T_{L(\varpi)}(\zeta), I_{L(\varpi)}(\zeta), F_{L(\varpi)}(\zeta)), g_{L(\varpi)}(\zeta), g_L \in O_G, \zeta \in \Sigma, \varpi \in L\}$$

where $T_L, I_L, F_L \in [0, 1]$ are the truth membership degree, indeterminacy membership degree, and falsity membership degree respectively.

2.1. Single-Valued Neutrosophic N-Soft Sets

Definition 2.8. Let Σ be the initial universal set and K be the set of parameters under consideration, and $L \subseteq K$. Let $O_G = \{0, 1, 2, \dots, N - 1\}$ be the collection of ordered grades where $N \in \{2, 3, \dots\}$. We say that (\mathfrak{N}, L, N) is a single-valued neutrosophic N-soft set (SVN_NSS) on Σ if $\mathfrak{N} : L \rightarrow 2^{SVNS(\Sigma) \times O_G}$, where $SVNS(\Sigma)$ is the collection of all single-valued neutrosophic sets over Σ . That is for each $\varpi \in L$,

$$\mathfrak{N}(\varpi) = \{(\langle \zeta, T_{\mathfrak{N}(\varpi)}(\zeta), I_{\mathfrak{N}(\varpi)}(\zeta), F_{\mathfrak{N}(\varpi)}(\zeta) \rangle, g_{\mathfrak{N}(\varpi)}(\zeta)) \mid \zeta \in \Sigma\}$$

where $T_{\mathfrak{N}(\varpi)}(\zeta)$ is the degree of membership, $I_{\mathfrak{N}(\varpi)}(\zeta)$ is the degree of indeterminacy, and $F_{\mathfrak{N}(\varpi)}(\zeta)$ is the degree of falsity of elements in Σ , and $T_{\mathfrak{N}(\varpi)}(\zeta), I_{\mathfrak{N}(\varpi)}(\zeta), F_{\mathfrak{N}(\varpi)}(\zeta) \in [0, 1]$, $g_{\mathfrak{N}(\varpi)}(\zeta) \in O_G$. For each $\zeta \in \Sigma$ and $\varpi \in L$, the element $(\langle \zeta, T_{\mathfrak{N}(\varpi)}(\zeta), I_{\mathfrak{N}(\varpi)}(\zeta), F_{\mathfrak{N}(\varpi)}(\zeta) \rangle, g_{\mathfrak{N}(\varpi)}(\zeta))$ is called the single-valued neutrosophic N-soft number (SVN_NSS).

Example 2.1. Suppose that $\Sigma = \{\zeta_1, \zeta_2, \zeta_3\}, K \supseteq L = \{\varpi_1, \varpi_2\}$. Define SVN₇SS as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} (\mathfrak{N}, L, 7) = \{\mathfrak{N}(\varpi_1) = \{(\langle \zeta_1, 0.8, 0.5, 0.2 \rangle, 3), (\langle \zeta_2, 0.9, 0.2, 0.5 \rangle, 5), (\langle \zeta_3, 0.6, 0.8, 0.4 \rangle, 6)\}, \mathfrak{N}(\varpi_2) \\ = \{(\langle \zeta_1, 0.4, 0.3, 0.5 \rangle, 6), (\langle \zeta_2, 0.7, 0.4, 0.8 \rangle, 3), (\langle \zeta_3, 0.5, 0.7, 0.3 \rangle, 4)\} \end{aligned}$$

The matrix representation of the SVN₇SS $[\mathfrak{N}, L, 7]$ is given as follows:

$$[\mathfrak{N}, L, 7] = \begin{matrix} & \varpi_1 & \varpi_2 \\ \begin{matrix} \zeta_1 \\ \zeta_2 \\ \zeta_3 \end{matrix} & \begin{bmatrix} (\langle 0.8, 0.5, 0.2 \rangle, 3) & (\langle 0.4, 0.3, 0.5 \rangle, 6) \\ (\langle 0.9, 0.2, 0.5 \rangle, 5) & (\langle 0.7, 0.4, 0.8 \rangle, 3) \\ (\langle 0.6, 0.8, 0.4 \rangle, 6) & (\langle 0.5, 0.7, 0.3 \rangle, 4) \end{bmatrix} \end{matrix}$$

Definition 2.9. Let (\mathfrak{N}_1, L_1, N) and (\mathfrak{N}_2, L_2, N) be two SVN_NSSs over Σ , where $L_1, L_2 \subseteq K$ and $N \in O_G$. Then the algebraic sum of (\mathfrak{N}_1, L_1, N) and (\mathfrak{N}_2, L_2, N) is an SVN_NSS, denoted by $(\mathfrak{N}_1, L_1, N) \boxplus (\mathfrak{N}_2, L_2, N)$, is defined as follows:

$$(\mathfrak{N}_1, L_1, N) \boxplus (\mathfrak{N}_2, L_2, N) = (\mathfrak{N}, L, N)$$

Where $L = L_1 \cup L_2$ and

$$\mathfrak{N}(\varpi) = \begin{cases} \mathfrak{N}_1(\varpi); & \text{if } \varpi \in L_1 - L_2 \\ \mathfrak{N}_2(\varpi); & \text{if } \varpi \in L_2 - L_1 \\ \mathfrak{N}_1(\varpi) \boxplus \mathfrak{N}_2(\varpi); & \text{if } \varpi \in L_1 \cap L_2 \end{cases}$$

Where

$$\begin{aligned} \mathfrak{N}_1(\varpi) \boxplus \mathfrak{N}_2(\varpi) = \{(\langle \zeta, T_{\mathfrak{N}_1(\varpi)}(\zeta) + T_{\mathfrak{N}_2(\varpi)}(\zeta) - T_{\mathfrak{N}_1(\varpi)}(\zeta) \cdot T_{\mathfrak{N}_2(\varpi)}(\zeta), I_{\mathfrak{N}_1(\varpi)}(\zeta) \cdot I_{\mathfrak{N}_2(\varpi)}(\zeta), \\ (\zeta). F_{\mathfrak{N}_2(\varpi)}(\zeta) \rangle, \max(g_{\mathfrak{N}_1(\varpi)}(\zeta), g_{\mathfrak{N}_2(\varpi)}(\zeta)) \mid \zeta \in \Sigma\} \end{aligned}$$

Example 2.2. Suppose that the universal set $\Sigma = \{\zeta_1, \zeta_2\}$ and the parameter set $K = \{\varpi_1, \varpi_2, \varpi_3, \varpi_4\}$ with $L_1 = \{\varpi_1, \varpi_2\}$ and $L_2 = \{\varpi_2, \varpi_3\}$ are two subsets of K . Consider two SVN₅SSs $(\mathfrak{N}_1, L_1, 5)$ and $(\mathfrak{N}_2, L_2, 5)$ as follows:

$$[\mathfrak{N}_1, L_1, 5] = \begin{matrix} & \varpi_1 & \varpi_2 \\ \begin{matrix} \zeta_1 \\ \zeta_2 \end{matrix} & \begin{bmatrix} (\langle 0.5, 0.3, 0.4 \rangle, 4) & (\langle 0.5, 0.2, 0.4 \rangle, 2) \\ (\langle 0.7, 0.8, 0.9 \rangle, 3) & (\langle 0.6, 0.1, 0.2 \rangle, 3) \end{bmatrix} \end{matrix}$$

$$[\mathfrak{N}_2, L_2, 5] = \begin{matrix} & \varpi_1 & \varpi_2 \\ \begin{matrix} \zeta_1 \\ \zeta_2 \end{matrix} & \begin{bmatrix} (\langle 0.3, 0.4, 0.9 \rangle, 1) & (\langle 0.5, 0.2, 0.4 \rangle, 2) \\ (\langle 0.8, 0.2, 0.7 \rangle, 4) & (\langle 0.2, 0.1, 0.5 \rangle, 2) \end{bmatrix} \end{matrix}$$

Then the algebraic sum $(\mathfrak{N}_1, L_1, 5) \boxplus (\mathfrak{N}_2, L_2, 5) = (\mathfrak{N}, L, 5)$ is given by

$$[\mathfrak{N}, L, 5] = \begin{matrix} & \varpi_1 & \varpi_2 & \varpi_3 \\ \zeta_1 & [(\langle 0.50, 0.30, 0.40 \rangle, 4) & (\langle 0.65, 0.08, 0.36 \rangle, 2) & (\langle 0.40, 0.50, 0.60 \rangle, 3)] \\ \zeta_2 & [(\langle 0.70, 0.80, 0.90 \rangle, 3) & (\langle 0.92, 0.02, 0.14 \rangle, 4) & (\langle 0.20, 0.10, 0.50 \rangle, 2)] \end{matrix}$$

Definition 2.10. Let (\mathfrak{N}_1, L_1, N) and (\mathfrak{N}_2, L_2, N) be two SVN_NSSs over Σ , where $L_1, L_2 \subseteq K$ and $N \in O_G$. Then the algebraic product of sum of (\mathfrak{N}_1, L_1, N) and (\mathfrak{N}_2, L_2, N) is an SVN_NSS , denoted by $(\mathfrak{N}_1, L_1, N) \boxtimes (\mathfrak{N}_2, L_2, N)$, is defined as follows:

$$(\mathfrak{N}_1, L_1, N) \boxtimes (\mathfrak{N}_2, L_2, N) = (\mathfrak{N}, L, N)$$

Where $L = L_1 \cup L_2$ and

$$\mathfrak{N}(\varpi) = \begin{cases} \mathfrak{N}_1(\varpi); & \text{if } \varpi \in L_1 - L_2 \\ \mathfrak{N}_2(\varpi); & \text{if } \varpi \in L_2 - L_1 \\ \mathfrak{N}_1(\varpi) \boxtimes \mathfrak{N}_2(\varpi); & \text{if } \varpi \in L_1 \cap L_2 \end{cases}$$

Where

$$\mathfrak{N}_1(\varpi) \boxtimes \mathfrak{N}_2(\varpi) = \{ \langle (\zeta, T_{\mathfrak{N}_1(\varpi)}(\zeta) \cdot T_{\mathfrak{N}_2(\varpi)}(\zeta), I_{\mathfrak{N}_1(\varpi)}(\zeta) + I_{\mathfrak{N}_2(\varpi)}(\zeta) - I_{\mathfrak{N}_1(\varpi)}(\zeta) \cdot I_{\mathfrak{N}_2(\varpi)}(\zeta), F_{\mathfrak{N}_1(\varpi)}(\zeta) + F_{\mathfrak{N}_2(\varpi)}(\zeta) - F_{\mathfrak{N}_1(\varpi)}(\zeta) \cdot F_{\mathfrak{N}_2(\varpi)}(\zeta), \min(g_{\mathfrak{N}_1(\varpi)}(\zeta), g_{\mathfrak{N}_2(\varpi)}(\zeta)) \mid \zeta \in \Sigma \}$$

Example 2.3. Consider Example 2.2. Then the algebraic product $(\mathfrak{N}_1, L_1, 5) \boxtimes (\mathfrak{N}_2, L_2, 5) = (\mathfrak{N}, L, 5)$ is given by

$$[\mathfrak{N}, L, 5] = \begin{matrix} & \varpi_1 & \varpi_2 & \varpi_3 \\ \zeta_1 & [(\langle 0.50, 0.30, 0.40 \rangle, 4) & (\langle 0.15, 0.52, 0.94 \rangle, 1) & (\langle 0.40, 0.50, 0.60 \rangle, 3)] \\ \zeta_2 & [(\langle 0.70, 0.80, 0.90 \rangle, 3) & (\langle 0.48, 0.28, 0.76 \rangle, 3) & (\langle 0.20, 0.10, 0.50 \rangle, 2)] \end{matrix}$$

Definition 2.11. Let (\mathfrak{N}, L, N) be a SVN_NSS over Σ . Then the scalar multiplication operation on (\mathfrak{N}, L, N) with the scalar $\lambda (\lambda > 0)$, denoted by $\lambda(\mathfrak{N}, L, N)$, is defined as

$$\lambda(\mathfrak{N}, L, N) = (\mathfrak{N}_\lambda, L, N) = \left\{ \left(\left\langle \zeta, 1 - \left(1 - T_{\mathfrak{N}(\varpi)}(\zeta)\right)^\lambda, I_{\mathfrak{N}(\varpi)}(\zeta)^\lambda, F_{\mathfrak{N}(\varpi)}(\zeta)^\lambda \right\rangle, g_{\mathfrak{N}_\lambda(\varpi)}(\zeta) \right) \mid \zeta \in \Sigma \right\}$$

Where,

$$g_{\mathfrak{N}_\lambda(\varpi)}(\zeta) = \begin{cases} [g_{\mathfrak{N}(\varpi)}(\zeta)^\lambda]; & \text{if } [g_{\mathfrak{N}(\varpi)}(\zeta)^\lambda] \leq N - 1 \\ N - 1; & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

Where, $[g_{\mathfrak{N}(\varpi)}(\zeta)^\lambda]$ is the greatest integer less than or equal to $g_{\mathfrak{N}(\varpi)}(\zeta)^\lambda$.

Example 2.4. Consider the SVN_7SS in Example 2.1. Suppose that $\lambda = 0.5$, then

1. The scalar multiplication operation $0.5(\mathfrak{N}, L, 7)$ is given by,

$$[\mathfrak{N}_{0.5}, L, 7] = \begin{matrix} & \varpi_1 & \varpi_2 \\ \zeta_1 & [(\langle 0.55, 0.71, 0.45 \rangle, 1) & (\langle 0.23, 0.55, 0.71 \rangle, 3)] \\ \zeta_2 & [(\langle 0.68, 0.45, 0.71 \rangle, 2) & (\langle 0.45, 0.63, 0.89 \rangle, 0)] \\ \zeta_3 & [(\langle 0.37, 0.89, 0.63 \rangle, 3) & (\langle 0.29, 0.84, 0.55 \rangle, 2)] \end{matrix}$$

2. The exponentiation operation $(\mathfrak{N}, L, 7)^{0.5}$ is given by,

$$[\aleph^{0.5}, L, 7] = \begin{matrix} & \varpi_1 & \varpi_2 \\ \zeta_1 & ((0.89, 0.29, 0.11), 1) & ((0.63, 0.16, 0.29), 2) \\ \zeta_2 & ((0.95, 0.11, 0.29), 2) & ((0.84, 0.23, 0.55), 1) \\ \zeta_3 & ((0.77, 0.55, 0.23), 3) & ((0.71, 0.45, 0.16), 2) \end{matrix}$$

3. The Single-Valued Neutrosophic N-Soft ELECTRE I Method

In this section, we develop a novel approach to group decision-making problems, called single-valued neutrosophic N-soft ELECTRE I, by combining the notion of SVN_NSS and ELECTRE method. This innovative method is very effective to solve the MCGDM problems with single-valued neutrosophic N-soft information.

3.1. The MCGDM Problem

As part of operations research (OR), MCGDM can rank the alternatives by considering many relevant criteria or parameters. For an MCGDM problem involving single-valued neutrosophic N-soft information, let $\Sigma = \{\zeta_1, \zeta_2, \dots, \zeta_n\}$ be the set of alternatives with parameter set $K = \{\varpi_1, \varpi_2, \dots, \varpi_o\}$, and $D = \{d_1, d_2, \dots, d_p\}$ be the set of decision-makers. The decision-maker d_q ($q = 1, 2, \dots, p$) provides his evaluation data by combining the feasible alternative ζ_i , ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$) with the parameter ϖ_j , ($j = 1, 2, \dots, o$) under consideration, which is described by single-valued neutrosophic N-soft decision matrix $M^{(q)} = [m_{ij}^{(q)}]_{n \times o} = [\aleph_q, K, N]_{n \times o}$, where,

$$m_{ij}^q = \left\{ \left(\left(\zeta, T_{\aleph_q(\varpi_j)}(\zeta_i), I_{\aleph_q(\varpi_j)}(\zeta_i), F_{\aleph_q(\varpi_j)}(\zeta_i) \right), g_{\aleph_q(\varpi_j)}(\zeta_i) \right) \middle| \zeta \in \Sigma \right\}$$

That is, the SVN_NSDM

$$M^{(q)} = \begin{matrix} & \varpi_1 & \varpi_2 & \dots & \varpi_o \\ \zeta_1 & m_{11}^{(q)} & m_{12}^{(q)} & \dots & m_{1o}^{(q)} \\ \zeta_2 & m_{21}^{(q)} & m_{22}^{(q)} & \dots & m_{2o}^{(q)} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ \zeta_n & m_{n1}^{(q)} & m_{n2}^{(q)} & \dots & m_{no}^{(q)} \end{matrix}$$

Example 3.1. Suppose that $\Sigma = \{\zeta_1, \zeta_2, \zeta_3\}$, $K = \{\varpi_1, \varpi_2, \varpi_3\}$, and $D = \{d_1\}$. Take $N = 5$. Then

$$M^{(1)} = \begin{matrix} & \varpi_1 & \varpi_2 & \varpi_3 \\ \zeta_1 & ((0.8, 0.2, 0.3), 4) & ((0.7, 0.5, 0.2), 2) & ((0.9, 0.4, 0.2), 4) \\ \zeta_2 & ((0.7, 0.3, 0.4), 3) & ((0.8, 0.2, 0.1), 3) & ((0.3, 0.2, 0.4), 1) \\ \zeta_3 & ((0.4, 0.3, 0.4), 2) & ((0.6, 0.4, 0.3), 1) & ((0.4, 0.6, 0.1), 3) \end{matrix}$$

3.2. The Single-Valued Neutrosophic N-soft Concordance and Discordance Sets

The concordance and discordance sets are defined in the ELECTRE method as measures of satisfaction and dissatisfaction for the decision-maker when preferring an alternative over another. The alternative having greater the membership degree, lower the indeterminacy degree, lower the falsity degree, and greater the grade, is supposed to be superior to other available alternatives. The SVN_NS concordance and discordance sets are classified as strong, midrange, weak concordance and discordance sets.

Suppose that (\aleph_q, K, N) be an SVN_NSS over the universe Σ with parameter set K , and let ζ_μ and ζ_ν ($\mu, \nu = 1, 2, \dots, n, \mu \neq \nu$) be any two alternatives in Σ . Then the SVN_NS concordance set is the set of subscripts of those parameters about which ζ_μ preferred to ζ_ν and are classified as follows:

- 1) The SVN_NS strong concordance set $S_{C_{\mu\nu}}$:

$$S_{C_{\mu\nu}} = \{j | T_{\aleph(\varpi_j)}(\zeta_\mu) \geq T_{\aleph(\varpi_j)}(\zeta_\nu), I_{\aleph(\varpi_j)}(\zeta_\mu) \leq I_{\aleph(\varpi_j)}(\zeta_\nu), F_{\aleph(\varpi_j)}(\zeta_\mu) \leq F_{\aleph(\varpi_j)}(\zeta_\nu), \mathfrak{g}_{\aleph(\varpi_j)}(\zeta_\mu) \geq \mathfrak{g}_{\aleph(\varpi_j)}(\zeta_\nu)\} \tag{1}$$

- 2) The SVN_NS midrange concordance set $M_{C_{\mu\nu}}$:

$$M_{C_{\mu\nu}} = \{j | T_{\aleph(\varpi_j)}(\zeta_\mu) \geq T_{\aleph(\varpi_j)}(\zeta_\nu), I_{\aleph(\varpi_j)}(\zeta_\mu) \geq I_{\aleph(\varpi_j)}(\zeta_\nu), F_{\aleph(\varpi_j)}(\zeta_\mu) \leq F_{\aleph(\varpi_j)}(\zeta_\nu), \mathfrak{g}_{\aleph(\varpi_j)}(\zeta_\mu) \geq \mathfrak{g}_{\aleph(\varpi_j)}(\zeta_\nu)\} \tag{2}$$

- 3) The SVN_NS weak concordance set $W_{C_{\mu\nu}}$:

$$W_{C_{\mu\nu}} = \{j | T_{\aleph(\varpi_j)}(\zeta_\mu) \geq T_{\aleph(\varpi_j)}(\zeta_\nu), F_{\aleph(\varpi_j)}(\zeta_\mu) \geq F_{\aleph(\varpi_j)}(\zeta_\nu), \mathfrak{g}_{\aleph(\varpi_j)}(\zeta_\mu) \geq \mathfrak{g}_{\aleph(\varpi_j)}(\zeta_\nu)\} \tag{3}$$

Where $\{j = 1, 2, \dots, o\}$ is the collection of subscripts of all parameters under consideration. Each of these SVN_NS concordance sets signify the various extents of preference of ζ_μ and ζ_ν . In the case of SVN_NS midrange concordance set, the degree of indeterminacy of alternative ζ_μ is higher than the alternative ζ_ν , corresponding to the parameter ϖ_j . Therefore, when comparing $S_{C_{\mu\nu}}$ and $M_{C_{\mu\nu}}$, $S_{C_{\mu\nu}}$ is more concordant. Also, the degree of falsity of ζ_μ is greater than ζ_ν corresponding to the parameter ϖ_j . This implies that the SVN_NS midrange concordance set $M_{C_{\mu\nu}}$ is more concordant than the SVN_NS weak concordance set $W_{C_{\mu\nu}}$.

Example 3.2. Consider Example 3.1, The SVN_5S concordance sets are then computed and presented in matrix form as follows:

- 1) The SVN_5S strong concordance set $S_{C_{\mu\nu}}$:

$$S_C = \begin{matrix} & \zeta_1 & \zeta_2 & \zeta_3 \\ \zeta_1 & - & \{1\} & \{1\} \\ \zeta_2 & \{2\} & - & \{1,2\} \\ \zeta_3 & \phi & \phi & - \end{matrix}$$

- 2) The SVN_NS midrange concordance set $M_{C_{\mu\nu}}$:

$$M_C = \begin{matrix} & \zeta_1 & \zeta_2 & \zeta_3 \\ \zeta_1 & - & \{3\} & \{2\} \\ \zeta_2 & \phi & - & \{1\} \\ \zeta_3 & \phi & \{3\} & - \end{matrix}$$

- 3) The SVN_NS weak concordance set $W_{C_{\mu\nu}}$:

$$W_C = \begin{matrix} & \zeta_1 & \zeta_2 & \zeta_3 \\ \zeta_1 & - & \phi & \{3\} \\ \zeta_2 & \phi & - & \{1\} \\ \zeta_3 & \phi & \phi & - \end{matrix}$$

Similarly, the $SVN_N S$ discordant set is the collection of subscripts of those parameters about which ς_μ is not preferable than ς_ν , are classified as follows:

- 1) The $SVN_N S$ strong discordance set $S_{D_{\mu\nu}}$:

$$S_{D_{\mu\nu}} = \{j | T_{\aleph(\varpi_j)}(\varsigma_\mu) < T_{\aleph(\varpi_j)}(\varsigma_\nu), I_{\aleph(\varpi_j)}(\varsigma_\mu) > I_{\aleph(\varpi_j)}(\varsigma_\nu), F_{\aleph(\varpi_j)}(\varsigma_\mu) > F_{\aleph(\varpi_j)}(\varsigma_\nu), \\ g_{\aleph(\varpi_j)}(\varsigma_\mu) < g_{\aleph(\varpi_j)}(\varsigma_\nu)\} \tag{4}$$

- 2) The $SVN_N S$ midrange discordance set $M_{D_{\mu\nu}}$:

$$M_{D_{\mu\nu}} = \{j | T_{\aleph(\varpi_j)}(\varsigma_\mu) < T_{\aleph(\varpi_j)}(\varsigma_\nu), I_{\aleph(\varpi_j)}(\varsigma_\mu) < I_{\aleph(\varpi_j)}(\varsigma_\nu), F_{\aleph(\varpi_j)}(\varsigma_\mu) > F_{\aleph(\varpi_j)}(\varsigma_\nu), \\ g_{\aleph(\varpi_j)}(\varsigma_\mu) < g_{\aleph(\varpi_j)}(\varsigma_\nu)\} \tag{5}$$

- 3) The $SVN_N S$ weak concordance set $W_{D_{\mu\nu}}$:

$$W_{D_{\mu\nu}} = \{j | T_{\aleph(\varpi_j)}(\varsigma_\mu) < T_{\aleph(\varpi_j)}(\varsigma_\nu), F_{\aleph(\varpi_j)}(\varsigma_\mu) < F_{\aleph(\varpi_j)}(\varsigma_\nu), g_{\aleph(\varpi_j)}(\varsigma_\mu) < g_{\aleph(\varpi_j)}(\varsigma_\nu)\} \tag{6}$$

The $SVN_N S$ discordance set can be considered as the complementary subset of $SVN_N S$ concordance set. The alternative having lower the membership degree, higher the indeterminacy degree, higher the falsity degree, and lower the grade, is supposed to be greater discordant than the other alternatives. By considering the $SVN_N S$ midrange discordance set, the smaller the degree of indeterminacy of ς_μ than ς_ν implies that $S_{D_{\mu\nu}}$ is more discordant than $M_{D_{\mu\nu}}$. Moreover, since the degree of falsity of alternative ς_μ is smaller than the alternative ς_ν in $SVN_N S$ weak discordance set, $M_{D_{\mu\nu}}$ is more discordant than $W_{D_{\mu\nu}}$.

Example 3.3. Consider Example 3.1, The $SVN_5 S$ discordance sets are then computed and presented in matrix form as follows:

- 1) The $SVN_5 S$ strong concordance set $S_{D_{\mu\nu}}$:

$$S_D = \begin{matrix} & \begin{matrix} \varsigma_1 & \varsigma_2 & \varsigma_3 \end{matrix} \\ \begin{matrix} \varsigma_1 \\ \varsigma_2 \\ \varsigma_3 \end{matrix} & \begin{bmatrix} - & \{2\} & \phi \\ \{1\} & - & \phi \\ \{1\} & \{2\} & - \end{bmatrix} \end{matrix}$$

- 2) The $SVN_N S$ midrange concordance set $M_{D_{\mu\nu}}$:

$$M_D = \begin{matrix} & \begin{matrix} \varsigma_1 & \varsigma_2 & \varsigma_3 \end{matrix} \\ \begin{matrix} \varsigma_1 \\ \varsigma_2 \\ \varsigma_3 \end{matrix} & \begin{bmatrix} - & \phi & \phi \\ \{3\} & - & \{3\} \\ \{2\} & \phi & - \end{bmatrix} \end{matrix}$$

- 3) The $SVN_N S$ weak concordance set $W_{D_{\mu\nu}}$:

$$W_D = \begin{matrix} & \begin{matrix} \varsigma_1 & \varsigma_2 & \varsigma_3 \end{matrix} \\ \begin{matrix} \varsigma_1 \\ \varsigma_2 \\ \varsigma_3 \end{matrix} & \begin{bmatrix} - & \phi & \phi \\ \phi & - & \phi \\ \{3\} & \phi & - \end{bmatrix} \end{matrix}$$

3.3. The Single-Valued Neutrosophic N-soft Concordance and Discordance Index

3.3.1. The Single-Valued Concordance Index and Matrix

The means of weights given to the parameter involved in the appropriate concordance set determine the probable concordance index. Suppose that $\omega_j = ((T_\omega(\omega_j), I_\omega(\omega_j), F_\omega(\omega_j)), g_\omega(\omega_j))$ is the SVN_NS weights associated with the parameter ω_j , then the concordance index $CI_{\mu\nu} = ((T_{CI_{\mu\nu}}^{(j)}, I_{CI_{\mu\nu}}^{(j)}, F_{CI_{\mu\nu}}^{(j)}, g_{CI_{\mu\nu}}^{(j)}), (\mu, \nu = 1, 2, \dots, n, \mu \neq \nu)$ of the alternatives ζ_μ and ζ_ν defined as follows:

$$CI_{\mu\nu} = \omega_{S_C} \sum_{j \in S_{C_{\mu\nu}}} \omega_j \boxplus \omega_{M_C} \sum_{j \in M_{C_{\mu\nu}}} \omega_j \boxplus \sum_{j \in W_{C_{\mu\nu}}} \omega_j \tag{7}$$

where \sum denote the algebraic summation. ω_{S_C} , ω_{M_C} and ω_{W_C} are the weights given by the decision-makers, to the SVN_NS strong, midrange, and weak concordance sets respectively. The SVN_NS concordance index illustrate the relative dominance of the alternative ζ_μ over the alternative ζ_ν according to the Equation 7. Also a higher or lower value of $CI_{\mu\nu}$ suggests that ζ_μ has higher or lower dominance and concordance with ζ_ν . Then the SVN_NS concordance matrix $C_M = [CI, K, N]_{n \times n} = [CI_{\mu\nu}]_{n \times n}$ containing the concordance indices $CI_{\mu\nu}$ as entries can be assembled as follows:

$$C_M = \begin{matrix} & \zeta_1 & \zeta_2 & \dots & \zeta_{(n-1)} & \zeta_n \\ \begin{matrix} \zeta_1 \\ \zeta_2 \\ \vdots \\ \zeta_{n-1} \\ \zeta_n \end{matrix} & \left[\begin{array}{cccccc} - & CI_{12} & \dots & CI_{1(n-1)} & CI_{1n} \\ CI_{\mu\nu} & - & \dots & CI_{2(n-1)} & CI_{2n} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ CI_{(n-1)1} & CI_{(n-1)2} & \dots & - & CI_{(n-1)n} \\ CI_{n1} & CI_{n2} & \dots & CI_{n(n-1)} & - \end{array} \right] \end{matrix}$$

3.3.2. The Single-Valued Discordance Index and Matrix

The SVN_NS discordance indices illustrate how the ratings of alternative ζ_μ are significantly weaker than the evaluation of ζ_ν . The index $DI_{\mu\nu}$ is obtained for every element of the discordance set using the elements of aggregated weighted SVN_NS decision matrix $M = [m_{ij}]_{n \times n} = [K, K, N]_{n \times n}$, and is defined as follows:

$$DI_{\mu\nu} = (d_{\mu\nu}, g_{\mu\nu}) \tag{8}$$

Where,

$$DI_{\mu\nu} = \frac{\max_{(j \in S_{D_{\mu\nu}} \cup M_{D_{\mu\nu}} \cup W_{D_{\mu\nu}})} \{ \omega_{S_D} \cdot d(m_{\mu j}, m_{\nu j}), \omega_{M_D} \cdot d(m_{\mu j}, m_{\nu j}), \omega_{W_D} \cdot d(m_{\mu j}, m_{\nu j}) \}}{\max_{j \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\}} d(m_{\mu j}, m_{\nu j})} \tag{9}$$

$$g_{\mu\nu} = \max_{(j \in S_{D_{\mu\nu}} \cup M_{D_{\mu\nu}} \cup W_{D_{\mu\nu}})} |g_{K(\varpi_j)}(\zeta_\mu) - g_{K(\varpi_j)}(\zeta_\nu)| \tag{10}$$

($0 \leq d_{\mu\nu} \leq 1$), ($\mu, \nu = 1, 2, \dots, n, \mu \neq \nu$), ω_{S_D} , ω_{M_D} and ω_{W_D} are the weights of SVN_NS strong, midrange, and weak discordance sets respectively, given by the decision-makers. And

$$d(m_{\mu j}, m_{\nu j}) = \sqrt{\frac{1}{3} \left[T_{\kappa(\varpi_j)}(\zeta_\mu) - T_{\kappa(\varpi_j)}(\zeta_\nu) \right]^2 + \left[I_{\kappa(\varpi_j)}(\zeta_\mu) - I_{\kappa(\varpi_j)}(\zeta_\nu) \right]^2 + \left[F_{\kappa(\varpi_j)}(\zeta_\mu) - F_{\kappa(\varpi_j)}(\zeta_\nu) \right]^2} \quad (11)$$

The SVN_NS discordance index $DI_{\mu\nu}$, as defined by its formula, shows the relative difference in the performance of competing alternatives ζ_μ and ζ_ν in terms of discordance parameter. Also, the stronger objection to the assertion “ ζ_μ is at least as good as ζ_ν ”. Then the SVN_NS discordance matrix $D_M = [DI_{\mu\nu}]_{n \times n}$ can be constructed as follows:

$$D_M = \begin{matrix} & \zeta_1 & \zeta_2 & \dots & \zeta_{(n-1)} & \zeta_n \\ \begin{matrix} \zeta_1 \\ \zeta_2 \\ \vdots \\ \zeta_{n-1} \\ \zeta_n \end{matrix} & \begin{bmatrix} - & DI_{12} & \dots & DI_{1(n-1)} & DI_{1n} \\ DI_{\mu\nu} & - & \dots & DI_{2(n-1)} & DI_{2n} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots \\ DI_{(n-1)1} & DI_{(n-1)2} & \dots & - & DI_{(n-1)n} \\ DI_{n1} & DI_{n2} & \dots & DI_{n(n-1)} & - \end{bmatrix} \end{matrix}$$

Example 3.5. Consider Example 3.1, Then the discordance matrix D_M is computed as follows:

$$D_M = \begin{matrix} & \zeta_1 & \zeta_2 & \zeta_3 \\ \begin{matrix} \zeta_1 \\ \zeta_2 \\ \zeta_3 \end{matrix} & \begin{bmatrix} - & (0.501,1) & \phi \\ (1,2) & - & (0.334,2) \\ (0.259,2) & (0.227,2) & - \end{bmatrix} \end{matrix}$$

3.4 The Outranking Relations

To model the priorities among the pairs of alternatives, outranking relations are used. If there is significant evidence to believe that ζ_μ is preferable to ζ_ν or at least one is as excellent as the other, an alternative ζ_μ outranks the other alternative ζ_ν . The most flexible idea of SVN_NS outranking relation can be used to represent the objective of preference ranking of one alternative over the others in the procedure of multi-criteria decision-making.

3.4.1. The Single-Valued Neutrosophic N-Soft Effective Concordance Matrix

To effectively identify the preeminence among a given pair of alternatives in a concordant point of view, a comparison can be made between the indices in the SVN_NS concordance matrix C_M and the threshold value named concordance level, denoted as $\check{C}L = \left((T_{\check{C}L_{\mu\nu}}, I_{\check{C}L_{\mu\nu}}, F_{\check{C}L_{\mu\nu}}), g_{\check{C}L_{\mu\nu}} \right)$, and evaluated from the SVN_NS concordance indices as:

$$\check{C}L = \left(\frac{1}{n(n-1)} \left(\sum_{\substack{\mu, \mu \neq \nu \\ \nu, \mu \neq \nu}}^n \sum_{\substack{\mu, \mu \neq \nu \\ \nu, \mu \neq \nu}}^n T_{C_{I_{\mu\nu}}^{(j)}}, \sum_{\substack{\mu, \mu \neq \nu \\ \nu, \mu \neq \nu}}^n \sum_{\substack{\mu, \mu \neq \nu \\ \nu, \mu \neq \nu}}^n I_{C_{I_{\mu\nu}}^{(j)}}, \sum_{\substack{\mu, \mu \neq \nu \\ \nu, \mu \neq \nu}}^n \sum_{\substack{\mu, \mu \neq \nu \\ \nu, \mu \neq \nu}}^n F_{C_{I_{\mu\nu}}^{(j)}} \right), \left[\frac{1}{n(n-1)} \sum_{\substack{\mu, \mu \neq \nu \\ \nu, \mu \neq \nu}}^n \sum_{\substack{\mu, \mu \neq \nu \\ \nu, \mu \neq \nu}}^n g_{C_{I_{\mu\nu}}^{(j)}} \right] \right) \quad (12)$$

where $(\mu, \nu = 1, 2, \dots, n, \mu \neq \nu)$ and $\left[\frac{1}{n(n-1)} \sum_{\substack{\mu, \mu \neq \nu \\ \nu, \mu \neq \nu}}^n \sum_{\substack{\mu, \mu \neq \nu \\ \nu, \mu \neq \nu}}^n g_{C_{I_{\mu\nu}}^{(j)}} \right]$ is the greatest integer less than or equal to $\frac{1}{n(n-1)} \sum_{\substack{\mu, \mu \neq \nu \\ \nu, \mu \neq \nu}}^n \sum_{\substack{\mu, \mu \neq \nu \\ \nu, \mu \neq \nu}}^n g_{C_{I_{\mu\nu}}^{(j)}}$.

The probability of dominance of alternative ς_μ over ς_ν increases, when $CI_{\mu\nu}$ outperforms this concordant level $\check{C}L$. Each and every entries in the $SVN_N S$ concordance matrix C_M are compared with the concordance level $\check{C}L$, on the basis of this, the concordant Boolean matrix $\Lambda = [\Lambda_{\mu\nu}]_{n \times n}$ can be calculated as

$$\Lambda = \begin{matrix} & \begin{matrix} \varsigma_1 & \varsigma_2 & \dots & \varsigma_{(n-1)} & \varsigma_n \end{matrix} \\ \begin{matrix} \varsigma_1 \\ \varsigma_2 \\ \vdots \\ \varsigma_{n-1} \\ \varsigma_n \end{matrix} & \begin{bmatrix} - & \Lambda_{12} & \dots & \Lambda_{1(n-1)} & \Lambda_{1n} \\ \Lambda_{\mu\nu} & - & \dots & \Lambda_{2(n-1)} & \Lambda_{2n} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots \\ \Lambda_{(n-1)1} & \Lambda_{(n-1)2} & \dots & - & \Lambda_{(n-1)n} \\ \Lambda_{n1} & \Lambda_{n2} & \dots & \Lambda_{n(n-1)} & - \end{bmatrix} \end{matrix}$$

Where,

$$\Lambda_{\mu\nu} = \begin{cases} 1; \text{ if } CI_{\mu\nu} \geq \check{C}L (T_{CI_{\mu\nu}}^{(j)} \geq T_{\check{C}L_{\mu\nu}}, I_{CI_{\mu\nu}}^{(j)} \leq I_{\check{C}L_{\mu\nu}}, F_{CI_{\mu\nu}}^{(j)} \geq F_{\check{C}L_{\mu\nu}}, \text{ and } g_{CI_{\mu\nu}}^{(j)} \geq g_{\check{C}L_{\mu\nu}}) \\ 0; \text{ otherwise} \end{cases} \tag{13}$$

Example 3.6. Consider Example 3.1, Then the concordance level $\check{C}L$ and the concordant Boolean matrix Λ are calculated as follows:

$$\check{C}L = \langle (0.684, 0.177, 0.121), 3 \rangle$$

$$\Lambda = \begin{matrix} & \begin{matrix} \varsigma_1 & \varsigma_2 & \varsigma_3 \end{matrix} \\ \begin{matrix} \varsigma_1 \\ \varsigma_2 \\ \varsigma_3 \end{matrix} & \begin{bmatrix} - & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & - & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & - \end{bmatrix} \end{matrix}$$

3.4.2. The Single-Valued Neutrosophic N-Soft Effective Discordance Matrix

Another method involves evaluating elements in the discordance matrix D_M on the basis of discordance level in order to obtain the dominant data of alternatives from a discordant perspective. That is, to what extent is one alternative unsatisfactory to another. The discordance level $\check{D}L = (\check{d}_{\mu\nu}, \check{g}_{\mu\nu})$ can be calculated as follows:

$$\check{D}L = \left(\frac{1}{n(n-1)} \sum_{\mu, \mu \neq \nu}^n \sum_{\nu, \mu \neq \nu}^n d_{\mu\nu}, \left[\frac{1}{n(n-1)} \sum_{\mu, \mu \neq \nu}^n \sum_{\nu, \mu \neq \nu}^n g_{\mu\nu} \right] \right) \tag{14}$$

where $\left[\frac{1}{n(n-1)} \sum_{\mu, \mu \neq \nu}^n \sum_{\nu, \mu \neq \nu}^n g_{\mu\nu} \right]$ is the greatest integer less than or equal to $\frac{1}{n(n-1)} \sum_{\mu, \mu \neq \nu}^n \sum_{\nu, \mu \neq \nu}^n g_{\mu\nu}$ and $(\mu, \nu = 1, 2, \dots, n, \mu \neq \nu)$.

Since $DI_{\mu\nu}$ reflects the degree to which an alternative ς_μ is inferior to ς_ν , and when it exceeds the discordance level $\check{D}L$, it confirms the conclusion that ς_μ is absolutely not preferable than ς_ν . On the basis of discordance indices, the discordant Boolean matrix $\Omega = [\Omega_{\mu\nu}]_{n \times n}$ can be computed as

$$\begin{matrix} \varsigma_1 & \varsigma_2 & \dots & \varsigma_{(n-1)} & \varsigma_n \end{matrix}$$

$$\Omega = \begin{matrix} \zeta_1 \\ \zeta_2 \\ \vdots \\ \zeta_{n-1} \\ \zeta_n \end{matrix} \begin{bmatrix} - & \Omega_{12} & \dots & \Omega_{1(n-1)} & \Omega_{1n} \\ \Omega_{\mu\nu} & - & \dots & \Omega_{2(n-1)} & \Omega_{2n} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots \\ \Omega_{(n-1)1} & \Omega_{(n-1)2} & \dots & - & \Omega_{(n-1)n} \\ \Omega_{n1} & \Omega_{n2} & \dots & \Omega_{n(n-1)} & - \end{bmatrix}$$

Where,

$$\Omega_{\mu\nu} = \begin{cases} 0; & \text{if } DI_{\mu\nu} \geq \check{D}L(d_{\mu\nu} > \check{d}_{\mu\nu} \text{ and } g_{\mu\nu} > \check{g}_{\mu\nu}) \\ 1; & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \tag{15}$$

Example 3.7. Consider Example 3.1, Then the discordance level $\check{D}L$ and the concordant Boolean matrix Ω are calculated as follows:

$$\check{D}L = (0.387, 1)$$

$$\Omega = \begin{matrix} \zeta_1 & \zeta_2 & \zeta_3 \\ \zeta_1 & - & 1 & 0 \\ \zeta_2 & 1 & - & 0 \\ \zeta_3 & 0 & 0 & - \end{matrix}$$

3.4.3. Aggregated Outranking Boolean Matrix

By combining the effective concordance and discordance information of the outranking relationship among the competing alternatives in terms of different parameters, the aggregated outranking matrix can be obtained. In a corresponding manner, the aggregated Boolean outranking matrix $\Delta = [\Delta_{\mu\nu}]_{n \times n}$ can be defined as follows:

$$\Delta = \begin{matrix} \zeta_1 & \zeta_2 & \dots & \zeta_{(n-1)} & \zeta_n \\ \zeta_1 & - & \Delta_{12} & \dots & \Delta_{1(n-1)} & \Delta_{1n} \\ \zeta_2 & \Delta_{\mu\nu} & - & \dots & \Delta_{2(n-1)} & \Delta_{2n} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots \\ \zeta_{n-1} & \Delta_{(n-1)1} & \Delta_{(n-1)2} & \dots & - & \Delta \\ \zeta_n & \Delta_{n1} & \Delta_{n2} & \dots & \Delta_{n(n-1)} & - \end{matrix}$$

Where,

$$\Delta_{\mu\nu} = \Lambda_{\mu\nu} * \Omega_{\mu\nu} \tag{16}$$

A non-zero value of $\Delta_{\mu\nu}$ (That is 1) completely implies that the alternative ζ_μ has strict dominance over the alternative ζ_ν .

Example 3.8. Consider Example 3.1, Then the Boolean outranking matrix Δ is computed as follows:

$$\Delta = \begin{matrix} \zeta_1 & \zeta_2 & \zeta_3 \\ \zeta_1 & - & 1 & 0 \\ \zeta_2 & 0 & - & 0 \\ \zeta_3 & 0 & 0 & - \end{matrix}$$

3.5 Discription of Outranking Graph

A graph is a structure consisting of a collection of elements, some of which are “connected” in some way. The final phase of the ELECTRE 1 approach is to use the outranking matrix Δ to extract as much of a compact set of alternatives as feasible in order to find the best solution to the MCDM problem. Accordingly, a simple directed graph $G = (V, M)$ is drawn, where V denote the set of vertices representing the alternatives and M denote the set of edges. Then the following cases can be occur,

for any pair of alternatives ζ_μ and ζ_ν .

Case 1: $\Delta_{\mu\nu}= 1$; then draw an arc from ζ_μ to ζ_ν indicating that ζ_μ is performing better than ζ_ν . (That is, $\zeta_\mu > \zeta_\nu$)

Case 2: $\Delta_{\mu\nu}= 1$ and $\Delta_{\nu\mu}= 1$; then draw a two-way arrowed arc to represent the indifferent relationship between the alternatives ζ_μ and ζ_ν (That is $\zeta_\mu \approx \zeta_\nu$).

Case 3: $\Delta_{\mu\nu}= 0$; then there will be no arc connecting the two vertices, and the corresponding alternatives ζ_μ and ζ_ν are incomparable (That is $\zeta_\mu ? \zeta_\nu$).

4. Algorithm for Single-Valued Neutrosophic N-soft ELECTRE I Method

Step 1: The neutrosophic numbers are used to indicate the significance of decision-makers using linguistic terms. Let $N_q = (T_q, I_q, F_q)$ be the neutrosophic number corresponding to the SVN_NS number, for rating of decision-maker d_q . Then the weight of d_q can be computed as

$$\xi_q = \frac{1 - \frac{1}{2(N-1)} \sqrt{(N-1)^2 \left((1-T_q)^2 + I_q^2 + F_q^2 \right) + (N-1-g_q)^2}}{\sum_{q=1}^p \left(1 - \frac{1}{2(N-1)} \sqrt{(N-1)^2 \left((1-T_q)^2 + I_q^2 + F_q^2 \right) + (N-1-g_q)^2} \right)} \quad (17)$$

where $\sum_{q=1}^p \xi_q = 1$.

Step 2: Corresponding to each decision-maker d_q with weight $\xi_q (q = 1, 2, \dots, p)$, $M^q = [m^{(q)}]_{n \times o}$ is the SVN_NS decision matrix. To generate an aggregated SVN_NS decision matrix $\tilde{M} = [\tilde{m}_{ij}]_{n \times o} = [\tilde{\aleph}, K, N]_{n \times o}$ in a group decision-making technique, all the individual opinions of decision-makers must be united into a collective opinion. The aggregated SVN_NS decision matrix \tilde{M} can be obtained as follows:

$$\tilde{m}_{ij} = \left(\left\langle 1 - \prod_{q=1}^p \left(1 - T_{\aleph_q(\varpi_j)}(\zeta_i) \right)^{\xi_q}, \prod_{q=1}^p \left(I_{\aleph_q(\varpi_j)}(\zeta_i) \right)^{\xi_q}, \prod_{q=1}^p \left(F_{\aleph_q(\varpi_j)}(\zeta_i) \right)^{\xi_q} \right\rangle, \left\lceil \prod_{q=1}^p \left(g_{\aleph_q(\varpi_j)}(\zeta_i) \right)^{\xi_q} \right\rceil \right) \quad (18)$$

where $\left\lceil \prod_{q=1}^p \left(g_{\aleph_q(\varpi_j)}(\zeta_i) \right)^{\xi_q} \right\rceil$ is the greatest integer less than or equal to $\prod_{q=1}^p \left(g_{\aleph_q(\varpi_j)}(\zeta_i) \right)^{\xi_q}$. Here

$\tilde{m}_{ij} = \left(\left\langle T_{\tilde{\aleph}(\varpi_j)}(\zeta_i), I_{\tilde{\aleph}(\varpi_j)}(\zeta_i), F_{\tilde{\aleph}(\varpi_j)}(\zeta_i) \right\rangle, g_{\tilde{\aleph}(\varpi_j)}(\zeta_i) \right)$, $(i = 1, 2, \dots, n \ \& \ j = 1, 2, \dots, o)$. Thus the aggregated SVN_NS decision matrix $\tilde{M} = [\tilde{m}_{ij}]_{n \times o} = [\tilde{\aleph}, K, N]_{n \times o}$ can be constructed as follows:

$$\tilde{M} = \begin{matrix} & \varpi_1 & \varpi_2 & \dots & \varpi_o \\ \begin{matrix} \zeta_1 \\ \zeta_2 \\ \vdots \\ \zeta_n \end{matrix} & \begin{bmatrix} \tilde{m}_{11} & \tilde{m}_{12} & \dots & \tilde{m}_{1o} \\ \tilde{m}_{21} & \tilde{m}_{22} & \dots & \tilde{m}_{2o} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ \tilde{m}_{n1} & \tilde{m}_{n2} & \dots & \tilde{m}_{no} \end{bmatrix} \end{matrix}$$

Step 3: Each parameter has its own importance, which may not be equal. By combining all the opinions of decision-makers, a matrix of important degrees of the appropriate parameter is

constructed for the ranking of each parameter. Suppose that $\omega_j^{(q)} = \left(\left\langle T_j^{(q)}, I_j^{(q)}, F_j^{(q)} \right\rangle, g_j^{(q)} \right)$ is the $SVN_N S$ number assigned to the parameter ω_j by the decision-maker d_q . To find the weight ω_j of each parameter, the evaluation of decision makers on parameters are aggregated by using the following equation.

$$\omega_j = \left(\left\langle 1 - \prod_{q=1}^p (1 - T_j^{(q)})^{\xi_q}, \prod_{q=1}^p (I_j^{(q)})^{\xi_q}, \prod_{q=1}^p (F_j^{(q)})^{\xi_q} \right\rangle, \left[\prod_{q=1}^p (g_j^{(q)})^{\xi_q} \right] \right) \tag{19}$$

where $\left[\prod_{q=1}^p (g_j^{(q)})^{\xi_q} \right]$ is the greatest integer less than or equal to $\prod_{q=1}^p (g_j^{(q)})^{\xi_q}$, and $W =$

$[\omega_1, \omega_2, \dots, \omega_o]$ where $\omega_j = \left(\langle T_W(\omega_j), I_W(\omega_j), F_W(\omega_j) \rangle, g_W(\omega_j) \right), j = 1, 2, \dots, o$.

Step 4: The aggregated weighted $SVN_N S$ decision matrix $M = [m_{ij}]_{n \times o} = [K, K, N]_{n \times o}$ can be calculated using multiplicative operator

$$\begin{aligned} m_{ij} &= \tilde{m}_{ij} \boxtimes \omega_j \\ &= \left(\left\langle T_{\tilde{m}_{ij}}(\varsigma_i) \cdot T_W(\omega_j), I_{\tilde{m}_{ij}}(\varsigma_i) + I_W(\omega_j) - I_{\tilde{m}_{ij}}(\varsigma_i) \cdot I_W(\omega_j), F_{\tilde{m}_{ij}}(\varsigma_i) + \right. \right. \\ &\quad \left. \left. F_W(\omega_j) - F_{\tilde{m}_{ij}}(\varsigma_i) \cdot F_W(\omega_j) \right\rangle, \min \{ g_{\tilde{m}_{ij}}(\varsigma_i), g_W(\omega_j) \} \right) \end{aligned} \tag{20}$$

The aggregated weighted $SVN_N S$ decision matrix M can be created as follows:

$$M = \begin{matrix} & \omega_1 & \omega_2 & \dots & \omega_o \\ \varsigma_1 & m_{11} & m_{12} & \dots & m_{1o} \\ \varsigma_2 & m_{21} & m_{22} & \dots & m_{2o} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ \varsigma_n & m_{n1} & m_{n2} & \dots & m_{no} \end{matrix}$$

Step 5: Based on the membership degree, indeterminacy degree, falsity degree, and grade of alternative over different parameters, the $SVN_N S$ strong, midrange, weak concordance and discordance sets $S_{C_{\mu\nu}}, M_{C_{\mu\nu}}, W_{C_{\mu\nu}}, S_{D_{\mu\nu}}, M_{D_{\mu\nu}}$, and $W_{D_{\mu\nu}}$ can be computed by using equations 1-6 respectively.

Step 6: Compute the concordance index $CI_{\mu\nu} = \left(\langle T_{CI_{\mu\nu}}^{(j)}, I_{CI_{\mu\nu}}^{(j)}, F_{CI_{\mu\nu}}^{(j)} \rangle, g_{CI_{\mu\nu}}^{(j)} \right), (\mu, \nu = 1, 2, \dots, n, \mu \neq \nu)$ by utilizing Equation 7 and create the concordant matrix C_M .

Step 7: Compute the discordance index $DI_{\mu\nu} = (d_{\mu\nu}, g_{\mu\nu})$ by using Equation 8 and construct the discordance matrix D_M .

Step 8: Using Equation 12, calculate the concordance level $\check{C}L = \left(\langle T_{\check{C}L_{\mu\nu}}, I_{\check{C}L_{\mu\nu}}, F_{\check{C}L_{\mu\nu}} \rangle, g_{\check{C}L_{\mu\nu}} \right)$ to analyze the relative superiority of pairs of alternatives, and then construct the effective concordance Boolean matrix $\Lambda = [\Lambda_{\mu\nu}]_{n \times n}$ as per Equation 13.

Step 9: Using Equation 14, evaluate the discordance level $\check{D}L = (\check{d}_{\mu\nu}, \check{g}_{\mu\nu})$ to investigate the relative

non-dominance of two alternatives and then construct the effective discordance matrix $\Omega = [\Omega_{\mu\nu}]_{n \times n}$ as per Equation 15.

Step 10: Compute the aggregated outranking Boolean matrix $\Delta = [\Delta_{\mu\nu}]_{n \times n}$ by using Equation 16.

Step 11: To eliminate the less desirable alternatives and determine the most acceptable collection of alternatives, draw the directed outranking graph $G = (V, M)$ as described in Section 3.5.

The flowchart of the proposed single-valued neutrosophic N-soft ELECTRE I method is presented in Figure 1.

5. Numerical Example

To demonstrate the applicability of our proposed SVN_NS-ELECTRE I method, we address a site selection problem for launching a manufacturing plant in a group decision-making environment in this section.

5.1 Site Selection for a Manufacturing plant

Finding the appropriate location, in the right region, and a suitable plot of land is becoming highly relevant for most businesses. As the global economic environment in which a firm must make a location selection becomes more uncertain by the day, it is critical to make a solid and future-proof decision on where to locate a new manufacturing plant. Companies may begin the location selection process for a new manufacturing plant for a variety of reasons, including cost reduction, capacity expansion to facilitate business growth, entry into new markets, tapping into new labor pools, and rationalization following a merger or acquisition. The construction of a new manufacturing unit necessitates major investments and internal modifications. Because the investments are made over a lengthy period of time, the new location's impact should similarly be good for a long period of time. That is, if a location decision is made wrongly, the negative consequences will last for a long time. For the selection of a suitable location or site for a manufacturing unit, the following factors can be considered.

- Costs: Real estate, land, logistical costs, taxes, labor, and other pertinent aspects that can be transformed into money.
- The business environment quality: Factors that cannot be easily translated into currency but have a direct impact on the performance of the new activities. Consider labor availability, access, supplier availability, customs rules, and the simplicity with which you may conduct business.
- Risk: All external business disruption risk elements that a company cannot control but that could have a significant impact on future operations, such as inflation, transparency risk, currency exchange rate risk, natural disaster risk, and so on.

In this work, we find the best suitable site for a company to start their manufacturing unit. We have to choose the most convincing site from a set of six sites $\{\zeta_1, \zeta_2, \zeta_3, \zeta_4, \zeta_5, \zeta_6\}$, which are selected by some primary evaluations. The set $\Sigma = \{\zeta_1, \zeta_2, \zeta_3, \zeta_4, \zeta_5, \zeta_6\}$ is considered as the set of alternatives. The company mainly considers five important parameters of criteria $K = \{\varpi_1, \varpi_2, \varpi_3, \varpi_4, \varpi_5\}$ for the selection process. They are given as follows:

- ϖ_1 : Suitable size (The size of the site must exceed the minimum plant layout requirement. Unless

future plant expansions are planned, sites should not be much larger than the required size, as this has an impact on affordability.)

- ϖ_2 : Availability (The location should be for sale and free of encumbrances such as contamination or legal wrangling. It can take a long time to fix these issues.)
- ϖ_3 : Accessibility (The location should be easily accessible for delivering process equipment to the site, as well as for feed material and product transportation. Access should ideally not entail the construction of new roads, rail spurs, or bridges.)
- ϖ_4 : Affordability (The demanding price for the site should be reasonable and based on an evaluation. The selecting committee should establish a maximum price that they are ready to pay based on the project's profitability.)
- ϖ_5 : Political stability (If a development in a foreign country is taken into account, this may be applicable. It might refer to the government's continuous backing for a project or the facility's physical security.)

The following steps constitute the process for selecting an appropriate site for starting the manufacturing plant using the proposed single-valued neutrosophic N-soft ELECTRE I method, and here we are taking $N = 7$. In other words, the single-valued neutrosophic 7 soft ELECTRE I method for the site selection process containing the following steps:

Step 1: Computation of the weights of the decision-makers.

Suppose that there are four decision-makers $D = \{d_1, d_2, d_3, d_4\}$. Table 1 lists the linguistic terms utilized in the relative importance rating of experts, as well as the parameters that were examined. Using Equation 17, the weight of the decision-makers are calculated and listed in Table 2.

Table 1: Linguistic terms for the weights of experts and parameters

Linguistic terms	SVN ₇ S Number
Highly Important (HI)	$(\langle 0.9, 0.1, 0.2 \rangle, 6)$
Important (I)	$(\langle 0.8, 0.3, 0.1 \rangle, 5)$
Average (A)	$(\langle 0.6, 0.3, 0.4 \rangle, 3)$
Not Important (NI)	$(\langle 0.3, 0.7, 0.6 \rangle, 2)$
Highly Not Important (HN)	$(\langle 0.1, 0.8, 0.9 \rangle, 1)$

Table 2: The significance of decision-makers and their weights

D	Linguistic terms	SVN ₇ S Number	Weights (ξ_q)
d_1	A	$(\langle 0.6, 0.3, 0.4 \rangle, 3)$	0.2274
d_2	HI	$(\langle 0.9, 0.1, 0.2 \rangle, 6)$	0.3540
d_3	I	$(\langle 0.8, 0.3, 0.1 \rangle, 5)$	0.3166
d_4	NI	$(\langle 0.3, 0.7, 0.6 \rangle, 2)$	0.1020

Step 2: Construction of single-valued neutrosophic 7 soft aggregated matrix.

Linguistic terms for the weights of the parameters are given in Table 3. The evaluation information of the decision-makers with respect to the parameters under considerations are shown in Table 4. Then the corresponding SVN₇S decision matrices $M^{(1)}$, $M^{(2)}$, $M^{(3)}$, and $M^{(4)}$ are given as follows:

Table 3: Linguistic terms for the weights of alternatives

Linguistic terms	SVN ₇ S Number
Highly Preferable (HP)	$\langle (0.9, 0.1, 0.1), 6 \rangle$
Most Preferable (MP) Preferable (P)	$\langle (0.8, 0.2, 0.1), 5 \rangle$
Average Preferable (AP)	$\langle (0.7, 0.3, 0.4), 4 \rangle$
Un-Preferable (UP)	$\langle (0.6, 0.4, 0.5), 3 \rangle$
Most Un-Preferable (MU)	$\langle (0.4, 0.6, 0.8), 2 \rangle$
Highly Un-Preferable (HU)	$\langle (0.2, 0.8, 0.7), 1 \rangle$
	$\langle (0.1, 0.9, 0.9), 1 \rangle$

Figure 1: Flowchart of SVN_NS -ELECTRE I method

Table 4: The significance of decision-makers and their weights

D	Σ	ϖ_1	ϖ_2	ϖ_3	ϖ_4	ϖ_5
d_1	ζ_1	HP	P	P	AP	UP
	ζ_2	UP	MP	HP	AP	HP
	ζ_3	HP	HP	P	AP	HP
	ζ_4	HP	P	MU	P	UP
	ζ_5	P	MP	AP	HP	P
	ζ_6	P	HP	AP	P	P
d_2	ζ_1	AP	P	HP	MP	MP
	ζ_2	P	AP	HP	P	P
	ζ_3	MP	P	HP	HP	AP
	ζ_4	UP	AP	MP	P	AP
	ζ_5	P	AP	AP	P	P
	ζ_6	P	HP	MP	AP	P
d_3	ζ_1	HP	P	MU	AP	MP
	ζ_2	MP	P	HP	MP	P
	ζ_3	HP	AP	HP	MP	MP
	ζ_4	HU	P	AP	P	MP
	ζ_5	MP	HP	P	P	UP
	ζ_6	P	AP	AP	HP	P
d_4	ζ_1	P	MP	AP	MP	HP
	ζ_2	HP	MU	P	P	MP
	ζ_3	HP	P	MP	MP	P
	ζ_4	AP	HU	MU	P	MP
	ζ_5	P	P	AP	AP	MP
	ζ_6	AP	P	HP	MP	HU

$$M^{(1)} = [\aleph_1, K, 7] =$$

	ϖ_1	ϖ_2	ϖ_3	ϖ_4	ϖ_5
ζ_1	$(\langle 0.9, 0.1, 0.1 \rangle, 6)$	$(\langle 0.7, 0.3, 0.4 \rangle, 4)$	$(\langle 0.7, 0.3, 0.4 \rangle, 4)$	$(\langle 0.6, 0.4, 0.5 \rangle, 3)$	$(\langle 0.4, 0.6, 0.8 \rangle, 2)$
ζ_2	$(\langle 0.4, 0.6, 0.8 \rangle, 2)$	$(\langle 0.8, 0.2, 0.1 \rangle, 5)$	$(\langle 0.9, 0.1, 0.1 \rangle, 6)$	$(\langle 0.6, 0.4, 0.5 \rangle, 3)$	$(\langle 0.9, 0.1, 0.1 \rangle, 6)$
ζ_3	$(\langle 0.9, 0.1, 0.1 \rangle, 6)$	$(\langle 0.9, 0.1, 0.1 \rangle, 6)$	$(\langle 0.7, 0.3, 0.4 \rangle, 4)$	$(\langle 0.6, 0.4, 0.5 \rangle, 3)$	$(\langle 0.9, 0.1, 0.1 \rangle, 6)$
ζ_4	$(\langle 0.9, 0.1, 0.1 \rangle, 6)$	$(\langle 0.7, 0.3, 0.4 \rangle, 4)$	$(\langle 0.2, 0.8, 0.7 \rangle, 1)$	$(\langle 0.7, 0.3, 0.4 \rangle, 4)$	$(\langle 0.4, 0.6, 0.8 \rangle, 2)$
ζ_5	$(\langle 0.7, 0.3, 0.4 \rangle, 4)$	$(\langle 0.8, 0.2, 0.1 \rangle, 5)$	$(\langle 0.6, 0.4, 0.5 \rangle, 3)$	$(\langle 0.9, 0.1, 0.1 \rangle, 6)$	$(\langle 0.7, 0.3, 0.4 \rangle, 4)$
ζ_6	$(\langle 0.7, 0.3, 0.4 \rangle, 4)$	$(\langle 0.9, 0.1, 0.1 \rangle, 6)$	$(\langle 0.6, 0.4, 0.5 \rangle, 3)$	$(\langle 0.7, 0.3, 0.4 \rangle, 4)$	$(\langle 0.7, 0.3, 0.4 \rangle, 4)$

$$M^{(2)} = [\aleph_2, K, 7] =$$

	ϖ_1	ϖ_2	ϖ_3	ϖ_4	ϖ_5
ζ_1	$(\langle 0.6, 0.4, 0.5 \rangle, 3)$	$(\langle 0.7, 0.3, 0.4 \rangle, 4)$	$(\langle 0.9, 0.1, 0.1 \rangle, 6)$	$(\langle 0.8, 0.2, 0.1 \rangle, 5)$	$(\langle 0.8, 0.2, 0.1 \rangle, 5)$
ζ_2	$(\langle 0.7, 0.3, 0.4 \rangle, 4)$	$(\langle 0.6, 0.4, 0.5 \rangle, 3)$	$(\langle 0.9, 0.1, 0.1 \rangle, 6)$	$(\langle 0.7, 0.3, 0.4 \rangle, 4)$	$(\langle 0.7, 0.3, 0.4 \rangle, 4)$
ζ_3	$(\langle 0.8, 0.2, 0.1 \rangle, 5)$	$(\langle 0.7, 0.3, 0.4 \rangle, 4)$	$(\langle 0.9, 0.1, 0.1 \rangle, 6)$	$(\langle 0.9, 0.1, 0.1 \rangle, 6)$	$(\langle 0.6, 0.4, 0.5 \rangle, 3)$
ζ_4	$(\langle 0.4, 0.6, 0.8 \rangle, 2)$	$(\langle 0.6, 0.4, 0.5 \rangle, 3)$	$(\langle 0.8, 0.2, 0.1 \rangle, 5)$	$(\langle 0.7, 0.3, 0.4 \rangle, 4)$	$(\langle 0.6, 0.4, 0.5 \rangle, 3)$
ζ_5	$(\langle 0.7, 0.3, 0.4 \rangle, 4)$	$(\langle 0.6, 0.4, 0.5 \rangle, 3)$	$(\langle 0.6, 0.4, 0.5 \rangle, 3)$	$(\langle 0.7, 0.3, 0.4 \rangle, 4)$	$(\langle 0.9, 0.1, 0.1 \rangle, 6)$
ζ_6	$(\langle 0.7, 0.3, 0.4 \rangle, 4)$	$(\langle 0.9, 0.1, 0.1 \rangle, 6)$	$(\langle 0.8, 0.2, 0.1 \rangle, 5)$	$(\langle 0.6, 0.4, 0.5 \rangle, 3)$	$(\langle 0.7, 0.3, 0.4 \rangle, 4)$

$$M^{(3)} = [\mathfrak{K}_3, K, 7] = \begin{matrix} & \varpi_1 & \varpi_2 & \varpi_3 & \varpi_4 & \varpi_5 \\ \zeta_1 & \langle(0.9, 0.1, 0.1), 6\rangle & \langle(0.7, 0.3, 0.4), 4\rangle & \langle(0.2, 0.8, 0.7), 1\rangle & \langle(0.6, 0.4, 0.5), 3\rangle & \langle(0.8, 0.2, 0.1), 5\rangle \\ \zeta_2 & \langle(0.8, 0.2, 0.1), 5\rangle & \langle(0.7, 0.3, 0.4), 4\rangle & \langle(0.9, 0.1, 0.1), 6\rangle & \langle(0.8, 0.2, 0.1), 5\rangle & \langle(0.7, 0.3, 0.4), 4\rangle \\ \zeta_3 & \langle(0.9, 0.1, 0.1), 6\rangle & \langle(0.6, 0.4, 0.5), 3\rangle & \langle(0.9, 0.1, 0.1), 6\rangle & \langle(0.8, 0.2, 0.1), 5\rangle & \langle(0.8, 0.2, 0.1), 5\rangle \\ \zeta_4 & \langle(0.1, 0.9, 0.9), 1\rangle & \langle(0.7, 0.3, 0.4), 4\rangle & \langle(0.6, 0.4, 0.5), 3\rangle & \langle(0.7, 0.3, 0.4), 4\rangle & \langle(0.8, 0.2, 0.1), 5\rangle \\ \zeta_5 & \langle(0.8, 0.2, 0.1), 5\rangle & \langle(0.9, 0.1, 0.1), 6\rangle & \langle(0.7, 0.3, 0.4), 4\rangle & \langle(0.7, 0.3, 0.4), 4\rangle & \langle(0.4, 0.6, 0.8), 2\rangle \\ \zeta_6 & \langle(0.7, 0.3, 0.4), 4\rangle & \langle(0.6, 0.4, 0.5), 3\rangle & \langle(0.6, 0.4, 0.5), 3\rangle & \langle(0.9, 0.1, 0.1), 6\rangle & \langle(0.7, 0.3, 0.4), 4\rangle \end{matrix}$$

$$M^{(4)} = [\mathfrak{K}_4, K, 7] = \begin{matrix} & \varpi_1 & \varpi_2 & \varpi_3 & \varpi_4 & \varpi_5 \\ \zeta_1 & \langle(0.7, 0.3, 0.4), 4\rangle & \langle(0.8, 0.2, 0.1), 5\rangle & \langle(0.6, 0.4, 0.5), 3\rangle & \langle(0.8, 0.2, 0.1), 5\rangle & \langle(0.9, 0.1, 0.1), 6\rangle \\ \zeta_2 & \langle(0.9, 0.1, 0.1), 6\rangle & \langle(0.2, 0.8, 0.7), 1\rangle & \langle(0.7, 0.3, 0.4), 4\rangle & \langle(0.7, 0.3, 0.4), 4\rangle & \langle(0.8, 0.2, 0.1), 5\rangle \\ \zeta_3 & \langle(0.9, 0.1, 0.1), 6\rangle & \langle(0.7, 0.3, 0.4), 4\rangle & \langle(0.8, 0.2, 0.1), 5\rangle & \langle(0.8, 0.2, 0.1), 5\rangle & \langle(0.7, 0.3, 0.4), 4\rangle \\ \zeta_4 & \langle(0.6, 0.4, 0.5), 3\rangle & \langle(0.1, 0.9, 0.9), 1\rangle & \langle(0.2, 0.8, 0.7), 1\rangle & \langle(0.7, 0.3, 0.4), 4\rangle & \langle(0.8, 0.2, 0.1), 5\rangle \\ \zeta_5 & \langle(0.7, 0.3, 0.4), 4\rangle & \langle(0.7, 0.3, 0.4), 4\rangle & \langle(0.6, 0.4, 0.5), 3\rangle & \langle(0.6, 0.4, 0.5), 3\rangle & \langle(0.8, 0.2, 0.1), 5\rangle \\ \zeta_6 & \langle(0.6, 0.4, 0.5), 3\rangle & \langle(0.7, 0.3, 0.4), 4\rangle & \langle(0.9, 0.1, 0.1), 6\rangle & \langle(0.8, 0.2, 0.1), 5\rangle & \langle(0.1, 0.9, 0.9), 1\rangle \end{matrix}$$

Now, the aggregated SVN₇S decision matrix $\tilde{M} = [\tilde{\mathfrak{K}}, K, 7]$ is constructed by using Equation 18 and is given below.

$$\tilde{M} = [\tilde{\mathfrak{K}}, K, 7] = \begin{matrix} & \varpi_1 & \varpi_2 & \varpi_3 & \varpi_4 & \varpi_5 \\ \zeta_1 & \langle(0.817, 0.183, 0.204), 4\rangle & \langle(0.712, 0.288, 0.347), 5\rangle & \langle(0.714, 0.286, 0.299), 2\rangle & \langle(0.708, 0.292, 0.240), 3\rangle & \langle(0.761, 0.239, 0.160), 4\rangle \\ \zeta_2 & \langle(0.724, 0.276, 0.262), 3\rangle & \langle(0.665, 0.335, 0.334), 3\rangle & \langle(0.888, 0.112, 0.115), 5\rangle & \langle(0.718, 0.282, 0.271), 4\rangle & \langle(0.776, 0.224, 0.253), 4\rangle \\ \zeta_3 & \langle(0.872, 0.128, 0.100), 5\rangle & \langle(0.744, 0.256, 0.313), 4\rangle & \langle(0.862, 0.138, 0.137), 5\rangle & \langle(0.816, 0.183, 0.144), 4\rangle & \langle(0.772, 0.228, 0.204), 4\rangle \\ \zeta_4 & \langle(0.564, 0.436, 0.493), 2\rangle & \langle(0.628, 0.372, 0.470), 3\rangle & \langle(0.607, 0.393, 0.316), 2\rangle & \langle(0.700, 0.300, 0.400), 4\rangle & \langle(0.672, 0.328, 0.284), 3\rangle \\ \zeta_5 & \langle(0.736, 0.264, 0.258), 4\rangle & \langle(0.786, 0.214, 0.204), 4\rangle & \langle(0.635, 0.365, 0.466), 3\rangle & \langle(0.759, 0.244, 0.299), 4\rangle & \langle(0.757, 0.243, 0.265), 3\rangle \\ \zeta_6 & \langle(0.691, 0.306, 0.409), 3\rangle & \langle(0.827, 0.173, 0.192), 4\rangle & \langle(0.728, 0.272, 0.240), 3\rangle & \langle(0.775, 0.225, 0.242), 4\rangle & \langle(0.664, 0.336, 0.434), 3\rangle \end{matrix}$$

Step 3: Calculation of the weights of parameters

The four decision-makers gave the weights of parameters under consideration in the form of linguistic terms, and are given in Table 5. The corresponding SVN₇S numbers are provided in table 6. Now, the weights of the parameters are calculated by aggregating the evaluation of decision-makers by using Equation 19. That is,

$$W = \begin{bmatrix} \omega_1 = \langle(0.805, 0.203, 0.198), 4\rangle^T \\ \omega_2 = \langle(0.825, 0.189, 0.183), 4\rangle \\ \omega_3 = \langle(0.866, 0.158, 0.150), 5\rangle \\ \omega_4 = \langle(0.768, 0.268, 0.166), 4\rangle \\ \omega_5 = \langle(0.837, 0.148, 0.256), 4\rangle \end{bmatrix}$$

Table 5: Weights of the parameters in linguistic terms

	d_1	d_2	d_3	d_4
ϖ_1	I	HI	A	I
ϖ_2	A	I	HI	HI
ϖ_3	HI	HI	I	I
ϖ_4	I	I	A	HI
ϖ_5	HI	A	HI	HI

Table 6: Weights of the parameters by decision-makers

	d_1	d_2	d_3	d_4
ϖ_1	$\langle\langle 0.8, 0.3, 0.1 \rangle, 5\rangle$	$\langle\langle 0.9, 0.1, 0.2 \rangle, 6\rangle$	$\langle\langle 0.6, 0.3, 0.4 \rangle, 3\rangle$	$\langle\langle 0.8, 0.3, 0.1 \rangle, 5\rangle$
ϖ_2	$\langle\langle 0.6, 0.3, 0.4 \rangle, 3\rangle$	$\langle\langle 0.8, 0.3, 0.1 \rangle, 5\rangle$	$\langle\langle 0.9, 0.1, 0.2 \rangle, 6\rangle$	$\langle\langle 0.9, 0.1, 0.2 \rangle, 6\rangle$
ϖ_3	$\langle\langle 0.9, 0.1, 0.2 \rangle, 6\rangle$	$\langle\langle 0.9, 0.1, 0.2 \rangle, 6\rangle$	$\langle\langle 0.8, 0.3, 0.1 \rangle, 5\rangle$	$\langle\langle 0.8, 0.3, 0.1 \rangle, 5\rangle$
ϖ_4	$\langle\langle 0.8, 0.3, 0.1 \rangle, 5\rangle$	$\langle\langle 0.8, 0.3, 0.1 \rangle, 5\rangle$	$\langle\langle 0.6, 0.3, 0.4 \rangle, 3\rangle$	$\langle\langle 0.9, 0.1, 0.2 \rangle, 6\rangle$
ϖ_5	$\langle\langle 0.9, 0.1, 0.2 \rangle, 6\rangle$	$\langle\langle 0.6, 0.3, 0.4 \rangle, 3\rangle$	$\langle\langle 0.9, 0.1, 0.2 \rangle, 6\rangle$	$\langle\langle 0.9, 0.1, 0.2 \rangle, 6\rangle$

Step 4: Formation of aggregated weighted SVN₇S decision matrix

The aggregated weighted SVN₇S decision matrix is calculated by using Equation 20, and is given as follows:

$$M = [\mathfrak{N}, K, 7] =$$

	ϖ_1	ϖ_2	ϖ_3	ϖ_4	ϖ_5
ς_1	$\langle\langle 0.658, 0.349, 0.362 \rangle, 4\rangle$	$\langle\langle 0.587, 0.423, 0.466 \rangle, 4\rangle$	$\langle\langle 0.618, 0.399, 0.404 \rangle, 2\rangle$	$\langle\langle 0.544, 0.484, 0.366 \rangle, 3\rangle$	$\langle\langle 0.637, 0.352, 0.375 \rangle, 4\rangle$
ς_2	$\langle\langle 0.583, 0.423, 0.408 \rangle, 3\rangle$	$\langle\langle 0.549, 0.461, 0.456 \rangle, 3\rangle$	$\langle\langle 0.769, 0.252, 0.248 \rangle, 5\rangle$	$\langle\langle 0.551, 0.474, 0.392 \rangle, 4\rangle$	$\langle\langle 0.650, 0.339, 0.444 \rangle, 4\rangle$
ς_3	$\langle\langle 0.702, 0.305, 0.278 \rangle, 4\rangle$	$\langle\langle 0.614, 0.397, 0.439 \rangle, 4\rangle$	$\langle\langle 0.746, 0.274, 0.267 \rangle, 5\rangle$	$\langle\langle 0.627, 0.402, 0.286 \rangle, 4\rangle$	$\langle\langle 0.646, 0.342, 0.408 \rangle, 4\rangle$
ς_4	$\langle\langle 0.454, 0.550, 0.593 \rangle, 2\rangle$	$\langle\langle 0.518, 0.491, 0.567 \rangle, 3\rangle$	$\langle\langle 0.526, 0.489, 0.419 \rangle, 2\rangle$	$\langle\langle 0.538, 0.488, 0.499 \rangle, 4\rangle$	$\langle\langle 0.562, 0.427, 0.467 \rangle, 3\rangle$
ς_5	$\langle\langle 0.592, 0.413, 0.405 \rangle, 4\rangle$	$\langle\langle 0.648, 0.363, 0.350 \rangle, 4\rangle$	$\langle\langle 0.550, 0.465, 0.546 \rangle, 3\rangle$	$\langle\langle 0.583, 0.444, 0.415 \rangle, 4\rangle$	$\langle\langle 0.634, 0.355, 0.453 \rangle, 3\rangle$
ς_6	$\langle\langle 0.556, 0.449, 0.526 \rangle, 3\rangle$	$\langle\langle 0.682, 0.329, 0.340 \rangle, 4\rangle$	$\langle\langle 0.630, 0.387, 0.354 \rangle, 3\rangle$	$\langle\langle 0.595, 0.433, 0.368 \rangle, 4\rangle$	$\langle\langle 0.556, 0.434, 0.579 \rangle, 3\rangle$

Step 5: Calculation of SVN₇S concordance and discordance sets.

The SVN₇S concordance and discordance sets are evaluated by using equations 1-6, and are given as follows:

1. The SVN₇S strong concordance set $S_{C_{\mu\nu}}$:

$$S_C = \begin{matrix} & \begin{matrix} \varsigma_1 & \varsigma_2 & \varsigma_3 & \varsigma_4 & \varsigma_5 & \varsigma_6 \end{matrix} \\ \begin{matrix} \varsigma_1 \\ \varsigma_2 \\ \varsigma_3 \\ \varsigma_4 \\ \varsigma_5 \\ \varsigma_6 \end{matrix} & \begin{bmatrix} - & \{1\} & \phi & \{1, 2, 3, 5\} & \{1, 5\} & \{1, 5\} \\ \{3\} & - & \{3\} & \{1, 2, 3, 4, 5\} & \{3, 5\} & \{1, 3, 5\} \\ \{1, 2, 3, 4\} & \{1, 2, 4\} & - & \{1, 2, 3, 4, 5\} & \{1, 3, 4, 5\} & \{1, 3, 4, 5\} \\ \phi & \phi & \phi & - & \phi & \{5\} \\ \{2\} & \{1, 2\} & \{2\} & \{1, 2, 4, 5\} & - & - \\ \{2, 3\} & \{2, 4\} & \{2\} & \{1, 2, 3, 4\} & \{2, 3, 4\} & \{1, 5\} \\ & & & & & - \end{bmatrix} \end{matrix}$$

2. The SVN₇S midrange concordance set $M_{C_{\mu\nu}}$:

$$M_C = \begin{matrix} & \begin{matrix} \varsigma_1 & \varsigma_2 & \varsigma_3 & \varsigma_4 & \varsigma_5 & \varsigma_6 \end{matrix} \\ \begin{matrix} \varsigma_1 \\ \varsigma_2 \\ \varsigma_3 \\ \varsigma_4 \\ \varsigma_5 \\ \varsigma_6 \end{matrix} & \begin{bmatrix} - & \phi & \phi & \phi & \phi & \phi \\ \phi & - & \phi & \phi & \phi & \phi \\ \phi & \phi & - & \phi & \phi & \phi \\ \phi & \phi & \phi & - & \phi & \phi \\ \phi & \phi & \phi & \phi & - & \phi \\ \phi & \phi & \phi & \phi & \phi & - \end{bmatrix} \end{matrix}$$

3. The SVN₇S week concordance set $W_{C_{\mu\nu}}$:

$$W_C = \begin{matrix} & \begin{matrix} \varsigma_1 & \varsigma_2 & \varsigma_3 & \varsigma_4 & \varsigma_5 & \varsigma_6 \end{matrix} \\ \begin{matrix} \varsigma_1 \\ \varsigma_2 \\ \varsigma_3 \\ \varsigma_4 \\ \varsigma_5 \\ \varsigma_6 \end{matrix} & \begin{bmatrix} - & \{2\} & \phi & \phi & \phi & \phi \\ \{4, 5\} & - & \{5\} & \phi & \phi & \phi \\ \phi & \phi & - & \phi & \phi & \phi \\ \phi & \phi & \phi & - & \phi & \phi \\ \{4\} & \{4\} & \phi & \{3\} & - & \phi \\ \{4\} & \phi & \phi & \phi & \phi & - \end{bmatrix} \end{matrix}$$

4. The SVN₇S strong discordance set $S_{D_{\mu\nu}}$:

$$S_D = \begin{matrix} & \zeta_1 & \zeta_2 & \zeta_3 & \zeta_4 & \zeta_5 & \zeta_6 \\ \begin{matrix} \zeta_1 \\ \zeta_2 \\ \zeta_3 \\ \zeta_4 \\ \zeta_5 \\ \zeta_6 \end{matrix} & \left[\begin{array}{cccccc} \bar{-} & \{3\} & \{3,4\} & \phi & \phi & \{3\} \\ \{1\} & \bar{-} & \{1,2\} & \phi & \{1,2\} & \{2\} \\ \phi & \phi & \bar{-} & \phi & \phi & \phi \\ \{1,2,5\} & \{1,3,5\} & \{1,2,3,5\} & - & \{1,2\} & \{1,2,3\} \\ \{5\} & \{3,5\} & \{3,5\} & \phi & \bar{-} & \phi \\ \{1,5\} & \{3,5\} & \{1,3,5\} & \phi & \{1\} & \bar{-} \end{array} \right] \end{matrix}$$

5. The SVN₇S midrange discordance set $M_{D_{\mu\nu}}$:

$$M_D = \begin{matrix} & \zeta_1 & \zeta_2 & \zeta_3 & \zeta_4 & \zeta_5 & \zeta_6 \\ \begin{matrix} \zeta_1 \\ \zeta_2 \\ \zeta_3 \\ \zeta_4 \\ \zeta_5 \\ \zeta_6 \end{matrix} & \left[\begin{array}{cccccc} \bar{-} & \phi & \phi & \phi & \phi & \phi \\ \phi & \bar{-} & \phi & \phi & \phi & \phi \\ \phi & \phi & \bar{-} & \phi & \phi & \phi \\ \phi & \phi & \phi & - & \phi & \phi \\ \phi & \phi & \phi & \phi & - & \phi \\ \phi & \phi & \phi & \phi & \phi & - \end{array} \right] \end{matrix}$$

6. The SVN₇S weak discordance set $W_{D_{\mu\nu}}$:

$$W_D = \begin{matrix} & \zeta_1 & \zeta_2 & \zeta_3 & \zeta_4 & \zeta_5 & \zeta_6 \\ \begin{matrix} \zeta_1 \\ \zeta_2 \\ \zeta_3 \\ \zeta_4 \\ \zeta_5 \\ \zeta_6 \end{matrix} & \left[\begin{array}{cccccc} \bar{-} & \{4\} & \{5\} & \phi & \{4\} & \{4\} \\ \{2\} & \bar{-} & \phi & \phi & \phi & \phi \\ \phi & \phi & - & \phi & \phi & \phi \\ \phi & \phi & \phi & - & \{3\} & \phi \\ \phi & \phi & \phi & \phi & \bar{-} & \phi \\ \phi & \phi & \phi & \phi & \phi & - \end{array} \right] \end{matrix}$$

Step 6: Computation of concordance index and formation of concordance matrix.

Let $(\omega_{S_C}, \omega_{M_C}, \omega_{W_C}) = (1, \frac{2}{3}, \frac{1}{3})$ be the weights of the SVN₇S strong, midrange, and weak concordance sets, respectively, given by the decision-makers. The concordance indices $CI_{\mu\nu}$ ($\mu, \nu = 1, 2, \dots, n, \mu \neq \nu$) is calculated using Equation 7, and constructed SVN₇S concordance matrix C_M , where entries are the concordance indices $CI_{\mu\nu}$ ($\mu, \nu = 1, 2, \dots, n, \mu \neq \nu$).

$$C_M = [CI, \varpi, 7] = \begin{matrix} & \zeta_1 & \zeta_2 & \zeta_3 & \zeta_4 & \zeta_5 & \zeta_6 \\ \begin{matrix} \zeta_1 \\ \zeta_2 \\ \zeta_3 \\ \zeta_4 \\ \zeta_5 \\ \zeta_6 \end{matrix} & \left[\begin{array}{cccccc} \bar{-} & ((0.891, 0.117, 0.112), 4) & \phi & ((0.999, 0.001, 0.001), 5) & ((0.968, 0.030, 0.051), 4) & ((0.968, 0.030, 0.051), 4) \\ ((0.955, 0.054, 0.052), 5) & \bar{-} & ((0.927, 0.084, 0.095), 5) & ((0.999, 0.001, 0.001), 5) & ((0.978, 0.023, 0.038), 5) & ((0.996, 0.005, 0.001), 5) \\ ((0.999, 0.001, 0.001), 5) & ((0.992, 0.010, 0.002), 4) & ((0.927, 0.084, 0.095), 5) & ((0.999, 0.001, 0.001), 5) & ((0.999, 0.001, 0.001), 5) & ((0.999, 0.001, 0.001), 5) \\ \phi & \phi & \bar{-} & \phi & \phi & ((0.837, 0.148, 0.256), 5) \\ ((0.893, 0.122, 0.102), 4) & ((0.983, 0.025, 0.020), 4) & ((0.825, 0.189, 0.183), 4) & ((0.999, 0.001, 0.001), 5) & \phi & \bar{-} \\ ((0.986, 0.019, 0.015), 4) & ((0.959, 0.051, 0.008), 4) & ((0.825, 0.189, 0.183), 4) & ((0.999, 0.001, 0.001), 5) & ((0.995, 0.008, 0.001), 5) & ((0.968, 0.030, 0.051), 4) \end{array} \right] \end{matrix}$$

Step 7: Computation of discordance index and formation of discordance matrix.

Let $(\omega_{S_D}, \omega_{M_D}, \omega_{W_D}) = (1, \frac{2}{3}, \frac{1}{3})$ be the weights of the SVN₇S strong, midrange, and weak discordance sets, respectively, given by the decision-makers. The discordance indices $DI_{\mu\nu}$ ($\mu, \nu = 1, 2, \dots, n, \mu \neq \nu$) is calculated using Equation 8, and constructed SVN₇S discordance matrix D_M , where entries are the concordance indices $DI_{\mu\nu}$ ($\mu, \nu = 1, 2, \dots, n, \mu \neq \nu$)

$$D_M = \begin{matrix} & \zeta_1 & \zeta_2 & \zeta_3 & \zeta_4 & \zeta_5 & \zeta_6 \\ \zeta_1 & \bar{ } & (1,3) & (1,3) & \phi & (0.1569,1) & (0.3016,1) \\ \zeta_2 & (0.4386,1) & \bar{ } & (1,1) & \phi & (4103,1) & (0.9976,1) \\ \zeta_3 & \phi & \phi & \bar{ } & \phi & \phi & \phi \\ \zeta_4 & (1,2) & (1,3) & (1,3) & \bar{ } & \phi & (1,1) \\ \zeta_5 & (0.4574,1) & (1,2) & (1,2) & \phi & \bar{ } & (1,2) \\ \zeta_6 & (1,1) & (1,2) & (1,2) & \phi & (0.5908,1) & \bar{ } \end{matrix}$$

Step 8: Calculation of single-valued neutrosophic 7 soft effective concordance matrix. Using Equation 12 and the single-valued neutrosophic 7 soft concordance indices, the concordance level $\check{C}L$ can be computed as:

$$\check{C}L = ((0.798, 0.038, 0.041), 3)$$

Now, the concordant Boolean matrix Λ can be calculated by using Equation 13, and given as follows:

$$\Lambda = \begin{matrix} & \zeta_1 & \zeta_2 & \zeta_3 & \zeta_4 & \zeta_5 & \zeta_6 \\ \zeta_1 & \bar{ } & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ \zeta_2 & 0 & \bar{ } & 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ \zeta_3 & 1 & 1 & \bar{ } & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ \zeta_4 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \bar{ } & 0 & 0 \\ \zeta_5 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 1 & \bar{ } & 0 \\ \zeta_6 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & \bar{ } \end{matrix}$$

Step 9: Calculation of single-valued neutrosophic 7 soft effective discordance matrix. Using Equation 14 and the single-valued neutrosophic 7 soft discordance indices, the discordance level $\check{D}L$ can be computed as:

$$\check{D}L = (0.5451, 1)$$

Now, the discordant Boolean matrix Ω can be calculated by using Equation 15, and given as follows:

$$\Omega = \begin{matrix} & \zeta_1 & \zeta_2 & \zeta_3 & \zeta_4 & \zeta_5 & \zeta_6 \\ \zeta_1 & \bar{ } & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ \zeta_2 & 1 & \bar{ } & 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 \\ \zeta_3 & 1 & 1 & \bar{ } & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ \zeta_4 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \bar{ } & 0 & 0 \\ \zeta_5 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 & \bar{ } & 0 \\ \zeta_6 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & \bar{ } \end{matrix}$$

Step 10: Formation of aggregated outranking Boolean matrix. The effective aggregated outranking Boolean matrix Δ is constructed using Equation 16, and given as:

$$\Delta = \begin{matrix} & \zeta_1 & \zeta_2 & \zeta_3 & \zeta_4 & \zeta_5 & \zeta_6 \\ \zeta_1 & \bar{ } & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ \zeta_2 & 0 & \bar{ } & 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 \\ \zeta_3 & 1 & 1 & \bar{ } & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ \zeta_4 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \bar{ } & 0 & 0 \\ \zeta_5 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & \bar{ } & 0 \\ \zeta_6 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & \bar{ } \end{matrix}$$

Step 11: Construction of the directed outranking graph. Based on the aggregated outranking Boolean matrix Δ , the directed outranking graph $G = (V, M)$ can be constructed, and shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Outranking relationships between sites under consideration

The ranking between the alternatives (sites) given in Table 7 by exploring the decision graph. Thus it can be observed that, the site ς_3 is more preferable than the other sites $\varsigma_1, \varsigma_2, \varsigma_4, \varsigma_5,$ and ς_6 for starting the manufacturing plant.

Table 7: Exploration of the directed outranking graph

Sites	Incomparable sites	Submissive sites	SVN ₇ S-ELECTRE I ranking
ς_1	$\varsigma_2, \varsigma_5, \varsigma_6$	ς_4	4
ς_2	ς_1, ς_6	$\varsigma_1, \varsigma_2, \varsigma_5$	2
ς_3	-	ς_4, ς_5	1
ς_4	-	$\varsigma_1, \varsigma_2, \varsigma_4, \varsigma_5, \varsigma_6$	5
ς_5	ς_1, ς_6	ς_4	3
ς_6	$\varsigma_1, \varsigma_2, \varsigma_5$	ς_4	4

5. Conclusion

ELECTRE is a traditional outranking-based MCDM methodology for obtaining the most preferable collection of alternatives, more optimal for the corresponding decision-making problem. In this paper, we proposed the SVN_NS -ELECTRE I method to deal with MCGDM problems. An algorithm based on the proposed method is presented along with a flowchart. The novel ELECTRE I technique for SVN_NS MCGDM demonstrates a new strategy to efficiently deal with problems in business management. Also, this established approach is projected to be beneficial in any group decision-making context, including industrial engineering, environmental management, and medical sciences. We hope to extend our work to SVN_NS-ELECTRE II method, and to other ELECTRE generalizations in group decision-making in the future due to the flexibility of the SVN_NS model.

5. Acknowledgements

During the development of the manuscript, the authors gratefully acknowledges the financial assistance provided by the University Grants Commission (UGC) of India. The authors also express their heartfelt gratitude to Al-Ameen College, Edathala, Aluva, Kerala, India, for providing a conducive research environment and the necessary infrastructure to carry out this work.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

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Received: Aug 11, 2024. Accepted: Nov 7, 2024